
Corporate Social Responsibility in Nigeria: A Reconsideration of Milton Friedman's Business Proposition

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Abstract

In relation to some selected Nigerian organisations, this paper examined the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) within the purview of Milton Friedman's doctrine of the supremacy of stakeholders over other interests in the functionality of organisations in relation to the society. Corporate social responsibility is the contribution of corporate bodies to the wellbeing of the societies where they operate with a view to ensuring a win-win situation for all and sundry. The paper employed the secondary desk research methodology. It found out that most Nigerian organisations while not overly supporting Friedman's position, merely pay lip service to social responsibility. Thus, the paper made recommendations to ensure that necessary improvements are made on organisational Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

Key Words: Key words: Corporate Social Responsibility, Business, Shareholders, Organisations, and Development.

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Introduction

Several decades past, Milton Friedman, an economics Nobel Laureate argued that “an organisation’s major concern should be how to make enough profit to enable it pay high dividends to the shareholders. The organisation which fails to make justifiable profits and pay high dividends to its shareholders out of concern for public opinion, is a great act of social irresponsibility” (Ogedengbe, 2005). Milton Friedman **asserts:**

“There is one and only one social responsibility of business—to use its resources and engage in activities designed to increase its profits so long as it stays within the rules of the game, which is to say, engages in open and free competition without deception or fraud.” (The New York Times Magazine, September 13, 1970)

Friedman submitted that the business of business is to make profit for its owners and not turn itself to some kind of social benefactor. He distinguished between the business and the individual hire who is an agent of the employer, the shareholders. For him, the doctrine of business social responsibility is misplaced both in principle and consequences. While he has no quarrels with individuals spending their money for social causes of their choice, he firmly argued that any business concern that does so engages in veiled double taxation against the stakeholders, shareholders, customers and employees whose money is being appropriated without consultation. His position was received with derision by the proponents of corporate social responsibility while others saw the contradictions in the act and therefore aligned with Friedman. This paper intends to examine Friedman’s arguments, the current status of corporate social responsibility in Nigeria and how time has changed since the recession that blew across the world at the turn of the 20th century and especially in Nigeria.

As the twentieth century was wounding down so was the much talked about and hotly debated corporate social responsibility practices especially after the global economic meltdown of 2008. Corporate social responsibility had held sway for many decades from its beginning as acts of charity, philanthropy and corporate giving. Every organisation, particularly those that are in the business of goods production, rendering services, distributive trades and even governments jostled to be seen as socially responsible entities.

Although nobody has been able to enact any laws for the practice of corporate social responsibility, Late Senator Uche Chukwumerije in 2005 tabled a piece of legislation in Nigeria's upper chamber, the Senate seeking to mandate companies to practice corporate social responsibility. The bill died for lack of support. Even then, the practice continues to witness a plethora of self-censorship, self-regulation and world-wide guidelines established with several monitoring agencies checking the level of compliance and actually applied social sanctions where possible. The United Nations in 2000 floated the Global Compact whose aim as stated by Kofi Anan was to: "Through the power of collective action, the Global Compact seeks to advance responsible corporate citizenship so that business can be part of the solution to the challenges of globalization (Adamolekun, 2007; Ogedengbe, 2005). The Global Compact though not a regulatory body seeks partnerships and mutually agreeable standards that will make business more humane and beneficial to the society in the critical areas of people, planet and profits. In 2010, the ISO 26000 which was specifically designed to espouse the holistic and interdependence of the entire spectrum of CSR 7 core subjects was unveiled. They include: organisational governance, human rights, labour practices, the environment, fair operating practices, consumer issues and community involvement and development. This is after many years of arguments for and against the practice of corporate entities taking the interest of the host communities and matters germane to the sustainability of the human race in stride as they pursue their business goals.

Adeyanju (2012) stated that corporate social responsibility has to do with an organization going out of his way to initiate actions that will impact positively on its host community, its environment and the people generally. It can be seen as a way of acknowledging the fact that some business fall outs have adverse effects on the citizens and society and making efforts to ensure that such negative impact are ameliorated. Also, Lord Holmes and Richard Watts (2010) define corporate social responsibility as "the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of the workforce and their families as well as local community and society at large."

CSR in Context of Nigeria and the World

In Nigeria, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has grown from mere buzzword of the 1960s and 1970s to its present critical and pervasive reality such that corporate bodies that are not practicing it may be unwittingly toying with their reputation and probably their bottom

line (Adamolekun, 2005). Corporate social responsibility has many names depending on the intent of the user organisation and the purpose such as corporate citizenship, corporate social investment, good citizenship, stakeholders' capitalism, enlightened self-interest, corporate accountability, sustainable development among others. However, the aims and objectives of CSR are basically the attempts by corporate bodies to develop a convivial relationship with their host communities.

To a considerable extent, it can be regarded as a fad for big organisations in Nigeria such as banks, manufacturers, telecommunication, oil and gas companies which talk so much about CSR just to create an image of socially responsible entities whereas they are far from being so. Companies that gross as much as N1 billion after tax in profits annually cannot be said to practice CSR with token scholarships, sales bonanzas, obscure community projects that may not amount to one per cent of their profits. Indeed, many of them are involved in charity philanthropy and sponsorship which are regarded as less altruistic and not commensurate with the benefits derivable from the communal resources and the dangers the people are exposed to. The reason for this is not farfetched as it could be situated in our history of dictatorial and much compromised governments, coupled with a government dominated businesses. This situation naturally allows the multinational and transnational corporations to get away with sharp practices that endanger the lives of the people especially in them matter of environmental pollution and human right abuses.

There are a few multinational companies in Nigeria that have taken social responsibility matters seriously enough to commit a certain percentage of their earnings to corporate giving and other philanthropic activities. Among such companies that are aiming at international social responsibility performance standards are Unilever, British American Tobacco, Mobile Telecommunication Network, First Bank, United Bank for Africa, Guarantee Trust Bank, Sovereign Trust Insurance, **Shell** Petroleum Development Company and the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation.

Corporate Social responsibility across the developed world has become the accepted standard for businesses and ignoring or irregular implementation of its principles and practices have clear consequences. The United Nations and its several organs as well as western nation

governments adhere strictly to the imperatives of social responsibility and have developed codes of conduct that are binding on all.

Presently, corporate social responsibility has been so ingratiated into business and governance such that in spite of its voluntary nature, the practice has become normal as it has proven times without number that it positively impact the bottom line and makes government more responsive to the needs of the people. Of course, this is not the case in most of the developing nations, particularly Africa where most of the governments are deficient in carrying out their basic responsibilities to the citizenry not to talk of the shark and exploitative business organisations that they ironically permit to commit blunder through acts of professional negligence which perpetuates poverty and deprivation which they pretend is of great concern to them. Whereas corporate social responsibility should be business of making society better, what we see in many instances are acts akin to businesses being self centred and reluctant to impact society positively.

Bowen (1953) noted that corporate social responsibility refers to the obligations of businessmen to pursue those policies to make those decisions or to follow those lines of relations which are desirable in terms of the objectives and values of the society. Frederick (1960) stated that “Social responsibility means that businessmen should oversee the operation of an economic system that fulfills the expectations of the people.” Davis (1960) argued that social responsibility is a nebulous idea but should be seen in a managerial context and asserted that some socially responsible business decisions can be justified by a long, complicated process of reasoning as having a good chance of bringing long-time economic gain to the firm, thus paying it back for its socially responsible acts. Ideal social responsibility programming has both ethical and philosophical dimensions. In India, for example, there exists a wide gap between categories of people, just as in other climes, in terms of income and standard of living as well as socio-economic status (Bajpai, 2001).

Goyder (2003) cited in Srivastava, Negi, Mishra, Pandey (2012) argued that industry in present age can no longer be regarded as a private arrangement for enriching shareholders which is what Milton Freidman tried to emphasise in his social responsibility business treatise. This is because it has become a joint enterprise in which workers, management, consumers, suppliers, the locality, government and trade union officials all play a part. If the

system which we know by the name private enterprise is to continue, some way must be found to embrace many interests that make up industry in a common purpose as postulated by the stakeholders theory of Edward Freeman (Ogedengbe, 2019). Social responsibility implies some commitment, through corporate policies and sustainable action to make the society better. This operational view of corporate social responsibility as stated by Wood (1991) is often times reflected in an organisation, company or firm's social performance which is assessed by how its societal relationships, social impact and the outcomes of its social responsibility policies and actions are managed. Social responsibility programmes, therefore, should be a collective effort by all the operatives in the organisation, pulling in the same direction for the projects to have maximum impact.

Bahl (1994) cited in Alabi and Ntukekpo (2012) argued that "...organizations planned active and continuous participation with and within a community to maintain and enhance its environment to the benefit of both the institution and the community" is a desirable goal for business to succeed and in response to the license to operate. It was further argued that if an organization does not see itself as a corporate citizen, who has obligations and responsibilities towards its host communities, then, it may never recognise the need for the practice of community relations which is a vital tool for corporate social responsibility practices.

In the case of TATA Group, Srivastava *et. al* (2012), TATA business group has always been a stickler for corporate social responsibility. In recognition of the need for the continuous presence of CSR, Jamsetji Nusserwanji, founder, TATA Group stated: "in a free enterprise, the community is not just another stakeholder in business but is in fact the very purpose of its existence." The founder, Nusserwanji, noted that TATA used to grant scholarships for further studies abroad. He also supported Gandhi's campaign for racial equality in South Africa. TATA Group has given the country its first science and atomic research centre. The wealth gathered by Nusserwanji and his sons in half a century of industrial pioneering effort formed but a minute fraction of the amount by which they enriched the nation. JamshedIrani, Director, Tata & Sons Ltd, said "the Tata credo is that 'give back to the people what you have earned from them'. So from the its inception, Nusserwanji and his family have been following this principle" (TATA Group's website www.tata.com). The TATA mantra for the functionality and attainment of corporate social responsibility is to ensure that every business

owes some level of responsibility towards the society, nation and the world in general with the provision of human, material and natural resources. But the question is can this be said of companies in Nigeria?

Even at the peak of corporate social responsibility popularity in Nigeria, majority of the transnational telecommunication companies, consolidated banks, manufacturers, multinational oil and gas giants and many more merely mouthed social responsibility statements without much action. The money they spent on advertisements were much higher than the value of the projects they inaugurated. In order words, self-promotion and branding were the motivation for most of the supposed social responsibility programmes. To worsen this poor and deceptive posture, most of the programmes were one-off and were unsustainable having not consulted the intended beneficiaries and therefore, projects were imposed on the communities (Oso, 2008).

Corporate bodies in Nigeria have not exhibited exceptional social responsibility best practices as their social responsibility programmes are philanthropic. Generalised statements of social programmes are made but all around, the evidences are thin on the ground. What people see more are the marketing, promotional and branding communication strategies disguised as social responsibility programmes. Most of the organisations have now established foundations to squarely deliver quantifiable, verifiable and sustainable social responsibility programmes for national development. Today, organisations and individuals have commenced the gradual movement to the more transparent, verifiable, robust and sustainable sequence of establishing foundations, just as has happened in the western world, which by nature have a more structured operational code. They will eventually play more critical roles in development where government has faltered. Currently some of the notable foundations in Nigeria are: MTN, Airtel, Dangote, TY Danjuma, Oando, and Tony Elumelu Foundations.

In Kenya, the Kenya Commercial Bank (KCB) practicalised banking in the community with its *Jijiri* programme. *Jijiri* in Swahili means let us employ ourselves. Through the programme which more than 4,500 individuals have accessed, KCB support young Kenyan entrepreneurs by training them on technical skills, providing financial education and helping them to register their activities. Significantly, KCB also provide loans to assist in further

growing these startup businesses (The Banker, 2018). The *Jiajiri* programme has brought many success stories and have changed the storylines of these entrepreneurs. The *Jiajiri* programme has proved so successful that the Kenyan government and other corporate and developmental bodies have expressed interest in joining in the KCB's effort. Importantly, the *Jiajiri* programme won KCB Banking in the Community Award at the 2018 The Banker Award in London.

Methodology

Mixed methods were used. The methods used are secondary methodology of desk research, interview and survey research. The desk research method provided the perspectives that corporate social responsibility had been examined by various scholars. This ensured that all parameters of corporate social responsibility were fully examined towards ensuring that logical elongated positions were analysed in this work. The interview examined present position of corporate social responsibility in a telecommunication company while the survey investigated the position of the sample on social responsibility in Nigeria regarding Milton Friedman's doctrine of the supremacy of the stakeholders.

Milton Friedman's CSR Business Perspective

Milton Friedman's theory of corporate social responsibility continues to raise concerns from businesses, governments, regulators and Non-Governmental organisations after several decades as to its real nature and societal value. This has largely been fueled by discussions about the social responsibility of business which always tend to focus on the ethical and economic aspects and of course the rather fuzzy definitions. As a result of the vague definitions, people confuse philanthropy with corporate social responsibility and many times call different things by that name, corporate social responsibility.

In the early years of industrial revolution in the West, philanthropy was the commonest strategy businesses employed to positively impact their immediate communities by acts of good citizenship for many decades. Over the years, these activities have now become part of the basic social responsibility strategies. Even then the dichotomy between philanthropy and social responsibility may never really achieve complete severance as the two continues to be linked both conceptually and in practice.

Skeptics often claim that businesses should focus on making more money and let the government or nonprofit organisations deal with social and environmental issues. Milton Friedman claimed that free markets, rather than companies, should decide what is best for the world. He believes that Adam Smith's "invisible hand" will do all the work to make everything better for the human race,

Another argument is that companies are meant to create products or provide services rather than handle welfare activities. They do not have the expertise or knowledge necessary for handling social problems the sceptics claim. Also, if managers are concentrating on social responsibilities, they may not be performing their primary duties for the company at full capacity. Such arguments tend to support the view that acts of being socially responsible could damage a company's competitiveness in the global marketplace. Cleaning up the environment, ensuring product safety, and donating money or time for welfare issues all raise company costs which are ultimately passed on to the consumers through the final prices of the products or services. While some customers may be willing to pay more for a product from a company that is socially responsible, others might not. This could place a company that is not acting in society's social interest at an economic disadvantage.

The toughnickel.com (2018) website reveals that the new theory in social responsibility is sustainability. This has to do with companies that are socially responsible who will outperform their peers or competitors by giving focusing more on societal problems as opportunities to build and accrue sustainable profits that would be beneficial to all concerned in the short and long run. The simplest argument for social responsibility is that it is the right thing to do and as the saying goes, it is a matter of enlightened self-interest which often is a win-win situation. Some of society's problems have been created by oil multinational corporations, big manufacturing companies such as pollution, poor environmental management, anti labour practices, poor service delivery, and poverty-level wages. It is the ethical responsibility of businesses to ameliorate these wrongs by executing meaningful and sustainable community programmes. In the precarious situation of climate change and the pervading pauperisation of the people by greed motivated leaders on the African continent, developing world and Nigeria, companies that are unresponsive to the urgent need to aid development in all ramifications may suffer reputational consequences and in the long run become a victim of a collapsed economic system and the concomitant legislations and

regulations which oftentimes may be anti-business. It is possible for companies to prosper and build shareholder value by creatively working to solve social problems. It can be a great way for a company to build positive public image and attract top talents in the industry.

Although Freidman hypothetically acknowledged some of the critical elements of corporate social responsibility such as “providing employment, eliminating discrimination, avoiding pollution,” his conclusion that business should avoid getting involved in these acts cannot be sustained in the present global realities. Ferrara (2018) states that “Milton Friedman’s argument that corporations refrain from engaging themselves in social and political issues is compelling. But his argument likely *does not* apply in today’s world, a world where “social consciousness” actually drives business.” After all, a recent evaluation of Freidman’s five decades old shareholder doctrine by Meyer Colin, Strein Leo and Jaap Winter (2020) shows evidence of the non- sustainability of the narrow stakeholder-centered preoccupation for profits has failed and imperilled society. The doctrine gradually pulled the corporations away from its enlightened self-interest that would have preserved the link with the real interests of their human investors for “sustainable growth, fair treatment of workers, and protection of the environment” and society at large. Post COVID-19, Meyer et al proposes a radical departure of adopting an all-embracing public benefit corporation (PBC) type intervention emplaced in America, where the companies are obligated by law to commit to a public purpose beyond profit. In this operational mode, the company is expected to balance its business interest with the fiduciary responsibilities of its directors and board as an affirmative duty to be “good corporate citizens and to treat all stakeholders with respect.”

As Dangote, Nigeria’s foremost business tycoon once said, that there is a convergence of all sectors, businesses, philanthropy and especially government that there is now an urgent need to step up to address the human capital challenges that Nigeria is facing.

CSR and Economic Impact; Nigeria Snap Study

Creative capitalism is an approach where governments, businesses, and nonprofits work together to stretch the reach of market forces so that more people can make profit, or gain recognition, doing work that eases the world iniquities (Bill Gates, Davos, 2008)

The import of Milton Freidman’s postulation that businesses should rather concentrate on growing its profits by improving its earning capacity dawned on Nigerian, howbeit without being conscious of it, when the recession wiped out all pretenses to corporate social responsibility programmes by the big companies. The noisy advertisements and plethora of awards all for social responsibility projects virtually quietened and disappeared. This may imply that whatever social responsibility programmes that were being touted were not sustainable and were mere acts of showmanship, branding and self-promotion. Peter Andrew commenting on companies’ penchant for regarding social responsibility as essentially philanthropy, admonishes business that it is not right that “the current economic and financial crises is a good excuse for implementing almost nothing of their social measures. Especially in economically unstable and underdeveloped countries, CSR is almost nil.”

In a recent Google snap survey, Wole Adamolekun (2018) examined the status of corporate social responsibility in Nigeria and the import of Milton Freidman’s postulation on corporate social responsibility and business, some of the responses are quite revealing. The survey revealed that the economic recession of 2015 impacted corporate social responsibility programmes negatively as most respondents affirmed this development (48.8 per cent). In a follow up interview, with a staff of Etisalat, now 9Mobile Nigeria, it was revealed that in a bid to ensure the company survives the recession, the company had to restructure its staff drastically thereby fueling more unemployment and its eventual succumbing to a buyout. With regards to adequate funding of social responsibility programmes, only 34 per cent said they are funded sufficiently while 32.2 per cent are not sure. Well, this shows that funding is a big issue as it was also corroborated when the general question about the challenges of social responsibility activities was asked: 66 per cent of the respondents stated that funding was the biggest challenge.

When the respondents were asked about the specific position of Milton Freidman doctrine on business and social responsibility, the study revealed that 40.4 per cent and 31.9 per cent, making 72.3 per cent of the respondents stated that they are in agreement with Milton Friedman’s proposition which states that the business of business is to use its resources and energy in activities designed to increase its profits for its owners so long as it is competitive and fraud free.

While it is obvious that businesses are better able to take on social responsibility activities on a sustainable basis when they are achieving the corporate objectives of producing quality products and rendering efficient services and therefore making money, it is also true that socially responsible companies add value to itself and significantly improve their bottom line when they take care of the environment and are people-centered. That is the case of TATA earlier discussed and entrepreneur-philanthropists such as Bill Gates, Dangote, MTN, Nobel, Mark Zuckerberg and Warren Buffet and many others that have set up foundations that are presently making a difference to the quality of human life.

Recommendations

The following recommendations may serve as a reawakening for the big businesses to re-strategise and adopt best practices in social responsibility:

- a) Nigerian businesses big or small should embrace sustainable and socially responsible business models that are people centered and development orientated.
- b) Government at all levels should create the enabling environment for businesses to thrive so that they will in turn play their part in generating employment along their value chain.
- c) The civil society, NGOs, businesses and media should be accountable to the people and promote sustainable social responsibility.
- d) Corporate social responsibility should not be restricted to the transnational and multi-national corporations, but it is indeed a grassroots bottom up service that involves everybody hence the preferred terminology, social responsibility.
- e) The businesses that will survive and rule the corporate world of the Millennials would be those that recognises the need to balance the business needs of the stakeholders with the imperative of social responsibilities in human, environmental public interest beyond profits.
- f) Government should also make conscious efforts to invest in human capital as it remains one of the best developmental strategies to adopt for economic system that truly reflect people's needs which is its social responsibility and a good strategy for all round sustainable development.

Conclusion

Corporate social responsibility is an idea that has come to stay. Its time is here and now. There is need to increase the awareness of this compelling phenomenon that increases the chance of society benefiting more from its abundant endowment by making institutions that control most of these resources to altruistically make conscious effort to redistribute the common wealth fairly and equitably. This is because social responsibility ought to vigorously focus on creating a just and balanced society, inspiring conscious competition, and building coalitions that create new and endless possibilities for sustainable national development.

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Adult Education Socio-Economic Relevance to the Development of Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Empowerment concepts that relate skills and knowledge to economic outcomes, has been one of the major concerns of adult education for decades. Skills and knowledge are certainly central attributes of a developing nation such as Nigeria. Given the limitations of education as a proxy for socio-economic and national development, adult education is an antidote. It is on this note that this study investigated the contributions of adult education socio-economic relevance to the development of Nigeria, a case study of Oyo state. The study adopted the descriptive survey of the ex-post facto type, a self-structured instrument with a reliability coefficient of 0.81 and was analysed using simple percentages and chi square inferential statistics. The study shows that adult education programmes significantly enhance the social and the economic development of the participants and the nation at large. However, poor awareness, mobilization and enrolment, high rate of drop-outs among adult learners, poor funding of adult and non-formal education as compared to its formal education counterpart, inadequate trained facilitators and inadequate facilities among other points overwhelm the socio economic relevance of adult education in Nigeria thereby impeding its contributions to the socio-economic development of the nation. The study recommends that all efforts aimed at improving the socio-economic status of the people and the nation should first not only consider adult education socio-economic programmes but also consider these identified problems and curb them to the barest minimum.

Word count: 232**Key words:** Adult Education, Socio-Economic, Relevance, Development

Introduction

The term 'adult education' denotes the entire body of knowledge organised under educational processes, whatever the contents, level and methods, whether formal or otherwise, whether they prolong or replace initial education in schools, as well as in apprenticeship, whereby persons regarded as adult by the society develop their abilities and enrich their knowledge. It also includes those who improve their technical or professional qualifications or turn them in a new direction and bring about changes in their attitudes or behaviour in the twofold perspective of full personal development and participation in balanced and independent social, economic and cultural development (Balatti & Falk, 2015). Adult education is thus an integral part of, a global scheme for life-long education and learning; it provides 'life-long education and learning', an overall scheme aimed both at restructuring the existing education system aimed at developing the entire educational potential outside the education system. It also creates an understanding of and respect for the diversity of customs and cultures, on both the national and the international planes where men and women are the agents of their own education, through continual interaction between their thoughts and actions (Balatti & Falk, 2015).

In the context of adult education, learning is far from being limited to the period of attendance at school. It includes acquisition of skills and knowledge, using all possible means for full development of the individual. It is the educational and learning process in which learners of all ages are involved in the course of their lives to become self-developed and self-reliant (Heidi & Katleen, 2015). Adult education is a powerful factor of economic development. It increases productivity and competitive economic improvement. It is a means of curbing the problems of exploitation of the poor and their exclusion from the mainstream of development in the society. No wonder the United Nations recommends thus, "Each Member State should recognize adult education as a necessary and specific component of its education system and as a permanent element in its social, cultural and economic development policy" (Heidi and Katleen, 2015).

Adult education promotes the creation of structures, the preparation and implementation of programmes and the application of educational methods which meet the needs and aspirations of all categories of adults, without restriction on grounds of sex, race,

geographical origin, age, social status, opinion, belief or prior educational standards. It should be recognized that although in a given situation or for a specific period, adult education may play a compensatory role, it is not intended as a substitute for adequate youth education which is a prerequisite for the full success of national educational development (Sharan & Youngwha, 2014). Adult education helps in eliminating the isolation of women from education in many countries where women are denied formal education from youth. It ensures equality of access and full participation of women in the entire range of educational activities, including those which provide training for qualifications leading to high level of responsibilities which have hitherto been reserved for men. Taking measures with a view to promoting participation in adult education and community development programmes by members of the most under-privileged groups, whether rural or urban, settled or nomadic, and in particular illiterates will help ensure functional literacy. Adult education also helps young people who have been unable to acquire an adequate standard of general educational qualification; migrant workers and refugees; unemployed workers, members of ethnic minorities. Persons suffering from physical or mental handicaps persons experiencing difficulties of social adjustment and those serving prison sentences can also take advantage of adult education (Sharan and Youngwha, 2014).

It is in this context, that the United Nations further recommends thus, “Member States should associate themselves with the search for educational strategies designed to foster more equitable relations among social groups”. The objectives and goals of adult education policy should be incorporated in national development plans; they should be defined in relation to the overall objectives of education policy and of social, cultural and economic development policies. There is an increasing emphasis on the importance of continuous education. The world is progressively facing the phenomenon of changing the focus from formal to non-formal education (Peter, 2008). Even though, it is assumed that formal education offers adequate knowledge necessary to people for successful job performance, rapid economic, technical, technological and social changes. It is impose to individuals the request for acquisition of new knowledge which might not be permanent unlike what adult and non-formal education has to offer where students learn at their individual pace without imposition to attaining functional literacy. Thus, adult education is more flexible and dynamic thus more reliable in satisfying educational needs of a human in modern age. Adult

and Non-formal education entails a wide range of activities taken with a view to acquire new or upgrade the existing knowledge (Peter, 2008).

The advantages of non-formal education are multifold, since they enable individuals to learn what suits them and what they need in order to improve their knowledge, techniques and skills (Bošković, 2016). Adult education as an indispensable tool for the achievement of meaningful socio-economic development of every nation. Adult education programmes are very relevant for the development of a literate, informed, skilled and healthy adult population that drives successful socio-economic development activities. Adult education programmes are veritable tools designed to equip adults who are the economically productive and active citizens with required knowledge, attitudes, skills and commitment needed for meaningful socio-economic development (*Festus & Adekola. 2016*).

Adult education can be used to help the unemployed persons, including the educated unemployed, adult education activities can be designed, in particular, to adapt or modify their technical or professional qualifications with a view to enabling them to find or return to employment and to promote a critical understanding of their socio-economic situation. It can be used to help the ethnic minorities, to enable them to express themselves freely, to educate themselves and their children in their mother tongues, to develop their own cultures and learn languages other than their mother tongues and to become vital in socio-economic development (Aderinoye, 2004; Bošković, 2016).

Adult education should be all embracing as it takes account of: incentives and obstacles to participation and learning specially affecting adults; the experience gained by adults in the exercise of their family, social and occupational responsibilities; the family, social or occupational obligations borne by adults and the fatigue and impaired alertness which may result from them. Adult education should also involve the ability of adults to assume responsibility for their own learning; the cultural and pedagogical level of the teaching personnel available; the psychological characteristics of the learning process; the existence and characteristics of cognitive interests. It should also include the use of leisure time. Adult education activities are normally planned and executed on the basis of identified needs, problems, wants and resources, as well as defined objectives. Its impact should be evaluated and reinforced by whatever follow-up activities

may be most appropriate to given conditions. Particular emphasis must be placed on adult education activities intended for an entire social or geographical entity, mobilizing all its inherent energies with a view to improving the advancement of the group and social progress in a community setting(Aderinoye, 2004; Bošković, 2016).

Nigeria has not fully recognized and taken advantage of what adult education has to offer. There is lack of required support towards adult education activities in the nation. The government sees adult and non-formal education as less important to its formal education counterpart. Public authorities, including Federal, State and Local Governments credit organizations, provident societies and national insurance agencies and other employers of labour in Nigeria have not been contributing to the development of adult education and are therefore not taking expected advantages of adult education for national development.

Also available resources, both material and human, have not been mobilized toward the development of adult education thus, impeding what it has to offer as benefits to the Nigerian society. Lack of funds is still a major obstacle to individuals' participation in adult education programmes in Nigeria. The participation of members of underprivileged social groups has not been well encouraged, thus, lowering the socio-economic development of Nigeria. Having realized this, attention must be drawn to the need to fully support the education of adults in the Nigerian society especially the adult rural dwellers who are direct subjects of socio-economic marginalization. There is need to assess the extent to which adult education programmes have liberated the people from the shackles of ignorance and thus improved their socio-economic status. This study therefore seeks to leverage on notable contributions of adult education to the socio-economic improvement of the nation by recommending some ways to further enhance adult education socio-economic relevance to the development of Nigeria.

Thus, this study is aimed at investigating the success of adult education in Oyo State as a template to measure adult education socio-economic relevance to the development of Nigeria. Among other things the study examined the level of availability of adult education basic literacy education and skills acquisition centers in Oyo state; it also assessed the extent of acceptability and participation of the people in adult education programmes in

Akinyele Local Government Area of the state; and determined the extent to which adult education programmes has helped to improve socio economic development of Oyo state; and finally the study identified ways of proffering solutions to the problems facing the provision of desired quality of adult education programmes in Nigeria.

Nigeria defines and patterns adult education reactively. Nigeria uses adult education as a response mechanism, a form of reactive instrument used to fight the shackles of cultural imperialism, adopting the behaviourist approach. Adult education materials in Nigeria are more content and teacher-centred than those of the developed world's such as Great Britain, with the exception of correspondence material which is adult educational learners centered (Aderinoye, 2004).

Aderinoye, Egunyomi, and Sarumi (2003) cited in Sarumi (2011:442) asserts that, 'Globally, education is perceived beyond a mere tool for development; but it is rather seen as a vaccine that could be used to curb deadly diseases, prevent or control terrorism and eradicate indices of underdevelopment in general' Traditionally, literacy has been commonly defined as the ability to read and write at an adequate level of proficiency that is necessary for communication but to Anyanwu cited by Aderinoye (2004) it is seen as a move to liberate the poor . More recently however, literacy has taken on several meanings: technological literacy, mathematical literacy, and visual literacy are just a few examples. While it may be difficult to gauge the degree to which literacy has an impact on an individual's overall happiness, one can easily infer that an increase in literacy will lead to the improvement of an individual's life and the development of societies (Aderinoye 2004).

The purpose of adult education in Nigeria include;

1. Empowerment - the implicit application of self-worth as realized in the social and cultural contexts. This is the hallmark of education for independence, traditional education for clarification of values, and education for nation building. The goal is to realize political, economic, social, or cultural ends.
2. To provide functional literacy; functional remedial education; further education; vocational in-service on the job training for professionals in order to improve their skills.
3. For women's development to ensure equity gender balance education.

4. for community development which includes the following:

- a. Integrated rural development to improve and increase per capita income and general welfare of the people.
- b. the process of communal integration where members discuss and define their needs and work towards meeting such needs by doing things in common

A close look at the purpose of adult education in Nigeria shows that adult education is an instrument for social, economic, and political development.

The world today is a “global village”, where holistic education is required for man to function effectively in ever changing world (Falase, 2003). Education serves as an instrument for the creation of new values, knowledge, attitudes, behaviour modification and acquisition of skills. Adult education is aimed at providing education for interested members of the public who wish to avail themselves with the privilege of furthering their education. Adult education is a key element in the development of any nation whether politically, socially, economically, culturally and technologically. This development can only take place if and when citizens are equipped with the necessary skills, knowledge and attitudes.

The fact has dawned on the leaders of all nations including Nigeria that adult and continuing education is the panacea for the present and future problems that might face the country (Adedokun, 2008). Adult Education is designed to assist people in the development and acquisition of skills on a continuous basis. It also makes educational opportunities easily available to individuals who though might not have dropped out of the formal school system, but are nonetheless unable to continue their learning after the initial educational process on a full time basis, especially those who want to combine work with study such as to continually contribute to the desired development of their individual society and the nation at large (Falase, 2003; Adedokun, 2008).

The idea behind adult education is premised on the fact that regardless of one’s work or the extent of level of education, one should not stop schooling, because new concepts, new skills, new tools and new knowledge keeps growing and emerging. However, education based on knowledge of yesterday will be inadequate to cope with the challenges and changes of today and tomorrow. Hence, Akinpelu (2002) believes

that one cannot do today's job with yesterday's tools and hope to be in business tomorrow. This is the reason why Aitchinson in Ingwu and Ad (2008) said that continuing education is a response to the constantly changing conditions of modern life. It must lead to the systematic acquisition, renewal, upgrading and completion of knowledge, skills and attitudes required by changes and thus enhance socio-economic development (Akinpelu, 2002; Ingwu and Ad, 2008).

Adult education programmes are designed to meet identified or expressed adult learning needs by taking full advantage of continuing education, vocational, occupational or professional skills such as learning computer, remedial programmes for senior school certificate examination (SSCE) University and Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME), attending conferences, seminars and workshops toward achieving desirable development in all ramifications (Akinpelu, 2002; Ingwu and Ad, 2008).

Furthermore, adult education is saddled with the responsibility of providing educational opportunities for all categories of individuals irrespective of whatever failure was earlier recorded, thereby ensuring continuity in education, ensuring the continued relevance of the individual in the society, ensuring the provision of access to education for all citizens, and helping to retrieve the economic wastage that early school leavers would have constituted. (Egunyomi, 2001). Challenges militating against the Achievement of Literacy for All and Socio-Economic Development in Nigeria include:

- Problems in primary education (low enrolment rates, high dropout rates, inadequate facilities, poor teaching/learning materials, non-relevant curriculum);
- Poor enrolment rates in adult literacy programmes;
- High dropout rates linked both to economic problems which force adult learners to abandon classes in favour of income-generating activities and to problems relating directly to the adult literacy programme such as lack of relevance, funding issues and low morale among adult literacy instructors;
- Literacy instructors not properly trained in facilitation skills and gender awareness;
- The exclusion of women from adult education programmes;
- Higher drop-out rates among women due to non-relevant curricula and competing demands;

- Poor access to adult education for "hard" to reach communities, such as nomads, fishermen and pastoralists, rural communities with poor access roads;
- Failure to sustain literacy rates due to poor resources, including equipment, materials and teachers, donor dependency and a negative perceived value of education;
- A poor literate environment that means that literacy skills are not maintained in the long term.

System theory, Von Bertalanffy, the proponent of this theory emphasized that real systems are open to, and interact with, their environments, and that they can acquire qualitatively new properties through emergence, resulting in continual evolution. Systems theory is relevant to this research work. In a situation where the nation as a system is facing some problems especially socio-economic crises connected with cybernetics, advanced fee fraud practices, kidnapping of students for huge ransom payment, raping of women in rural areas, education at all levels are losing its values. All these combine to make adult and non-formal education almost irrelevant. In a country with annual lack of adequate educational budgetary funds, adult education should be the surest remedy to ensure continuing educational system in the country.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design of the ex post facto type. The simple random sampling was adopted to select a sample of 50 respondents among Adult learners from ANFE Adult Literacy Centres: State Secretariats Ibadan and Eleyele Ibadan, UI Adult Literacy Centres: Emmanuel College, Orita UI, Ibadan and Bishop Phillips Academy Iwo Road Ibadan, Odogbo Barracks Literacy Centre: Odogbo Central Mosque Ojoo Ibadan. All in Oyo State. The study used a self-structured questionnaire. The face, content and construct validity of the instrument was ascertained. The reliability of the instruments yielded 0.82 Cronbach Alpha. The data was obtained by administration of instrument and oral interview, analyzed by the use of descriptive statistics of frequency count, simple percentage and Chi square inferential measurement.

Results and Discussions

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender, Age and Class (N=50)

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	13	26.0
Female	37	74.0
Age	Frequency	Percent
Below 30	11	22.0
30-60	36	72.0
61 and above	3	6.0
Class	Frequency	Percent
Beginners	0	0.0
Intermediates	37	74.0
Advance	13	26.0

Findings of the study as shown in table 1 indicate that female respondents made up the largest proportion as they accounted for 74.0% of the total respondents while their male counterparts made up the remaining 26%. Also, it reveals that respondents between the age bracket of 30 and 60 made up the largest proportion as it accounted for 72.0% of the total population followed by those within age grouped below 30 years which accounted for 22.0% while those that are 61 years and above made up the remaining 6.0%. Findings also shows that the largest proportion of the respondents were those in the intermediate class as they accounted for 74.0% of the total respondents with those in the advance class constituting the remaining 26.0%.

Table 2: Level of availability of adult education basic literacy education and skill acquisition centers in Oyo state (N=50)

Items	SA	A	D	SD	df	X ²	Sig	Remark
Literacy centers are available everywhere in the state just like the primary schools are situated at every nuke and craning of the state	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	22 (44%)	28 (56%)	6	58.69	.005	P<0.05
There are enough facilitators in the literacy centers	0 (0%)	3 (6.0%)	27 (54.0%)	20 (40.0%)				
The facilitators processes mastery of programme matters	15 (30.0%)	34 (70.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)				
Literacy programme is free	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	20 (40.0%)	30 (60%)				
Enrolment in this center requires no fee from each participating learners	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	28 (56.0%)	24 (34.0%)				
This center is open to all willing learners	28 (56.0%)	20 (40.0%)	2 (4.0%)	0 (0.0%)				
The adult education programme is structure to cater for all categories of learners	28 (56.0%)	18 (36.0%)	4 (8.0%)	0 (0.0%)				
Weighted Average								

Table 2 showed the extent to which basic literacy education was provided in some selected areas of Oyo state. There was perfect agreement in the extent to which basic literacy education is provided in the state in the area of availability of centre, facilitators, effectiveness of facilitators, programme fees and the programme structure. This is because the respondent's degree of disagreement to these questions was almost 100%. This implies that the basic literacy education is not being adequately provided in the state under study.

Though the respondents agreed to the tune of 92% that the few available facilitators processes the required mastery which is very important and worthy of commendation. More so, that the few available centers are open to all the willing learners and that the programme structures were designed to cater for all categories of learners but the adult literacy centers are not adequately available and the few available ones require enrolment fee.

Thus, only the learners that can afford the fee are welcome even though the centers are said to have been open to all. The table shows that all the seven variables are significant to the extent to which basic literacy education is inadequately provided in the state. This is because the calculated X^2 value of 58.687 is greater than table X^2 value of 9.488 at 0.005 level of significance. The implication of this is that any efforts aimed at improving socio-economic development of the state and the nation at large should consider the extent to which adult education basic literacy education and skill acquisitions are provided.

Table 3: The extent of acceptability and participation of the people in adult education programmes in Oyo State (N=50)

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Df	X ²	Sig	P
This programme is well accepted by me	53(53%)	40(40%)	5(5%)	2(2%)	7	61.8%	.019	P<0.05
My participation in this programme is pleasing to me	45(45%)	42(42%)	8(8%)	7(7%)				
Most of the people around me encourages me to carry on with the programme	20(20%)	13(13%)	30(30%)	37(37%)				
This programme is very important and should be accepted by all	30(30%)	13(13%)	42(42%)	15(15%)				
People around me usually speak well of the programme	12(12%)	10(10%)	45(45%)	33(33%)				
I can boldly recommend this center to potential adult learners	56(56%)	30(30%)	10(10%)	4(4%)				
The intense mobilization and encouragement from the organisers aid my participation	53(53%)	21(21%)	13(13%)	13(13%)				
Every individual illiterate can become literate through this programme	53(53%)	30(30%)	13(13%)	4(4%)				
Weighted Average	65.0%			35.0%				

The analysis of table 3 reveals a great acceptability and participation of the people in adult education programmes as respondents agreed to the tune of 65.0%

Table 4: The extent to which adult Education Programmes Improved Upon the Social and the Economic Development of Oyo State (N=50)

Items	SA	A	D	SD	df	X ²	Sig	P
The adult education programmes has help developed my skill to do more	30(30%)	37(37%)	20(20%)	13(13%)	3	32.667	.000	P<0.05
Through adult education programmes my economic activities has been improved	46(46%)	30(30%)	15(15%)	11(11%)				
Through adult education programmes the economic activities in this community has been improved	45(45%)	30(30%)	13(13%)	12(12%)				
My service has become more valuable as result of my participation in adult education programme	56(56%)	40(40%)	3(3%)	1(1%)				
My spouse/family members now value me than before as a result of my participation in adult education programme	30(30%)	44(44%)	16(16%)	10(10%)				
My behavior at my work place is now much more appreciated due to my participation in literacy programme	43(43%)	41(41%)	11(11%)	3(3%)				
Teachers in my school feel for students taking part in sports.	56(56%)	30(30%)	11(11%)	3(3%)				
I have leant to respect other peoples opinion and views	11(11%)	9(9%)	41(41%)	39(39%)				
Weighted Average		64.2%		35.8%				

The table 4 shows that adult education programmes significantly enhanced social and economic development of the participants; $X^2(3)=32.667$, $P<0.05$. Hence, any effort aimed at improving the socio-economic status of the people, state and country at large should consider and take full advantage of adult education and its various programmes as appropriate to the desired development. The result is further confirmed by the percentage respondents that agreed to the tune of 64.2%. Confirming the fact that engagement in adult education programmes significantly improved upon the socio-economic development of the nation.

Table 5: Problems facing the provision of desired quality of adult education programmes in the nation Nigeria and solutions to the identified problems (N=50)

Items	SA	A	D	SD	df	X ²	Sig	R
Poor awareness, mobilization and enrolment	20 (40.0%)	22 (44.0%)	4 (8.0%)	4 (8.0%)	5	62.25	.001	P<0.05
High rate of drop-out among adult learners	21 (42.0%)	20 (40.0%)	4 (8.0%)	5 (10.0%)				
Poor funding of adult and non-formal education as compared to its formal education counterpart	30 (60.0%)	20 (40.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)				
inadequate trained facilitators	25 (50.0%)	25 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)				
Inadequate facilities	27 (54.0%)	20 (40.0%)	3 (6.0%)	0 (0.0%)				
Majority of the facilitators are not full time employees. Thus, sometimes too busy to show-up when expected in the literacy class leading to discouragement among the learners	25 (50.0%)	15 (30.0%)	5 (10.0%)	5 (10.0%)				

Analysis of the above table shows that poor awareness, mobilization and enrolment, high rate of drop-out among adult learners, poor funding of adult and non-formal education, inadequate trained facilitators and inadequate facilities among others affect adult literacy education in Nigeria. Thus, impeding its contribution on the socio-economic development of the nation. The implication of this is that all efforts aimed at improving the socio-economic status of the people and the nation as a whole should firstly consider the identified problems and curb them to the barest minimum, else such programme may not achieve its objectives. The chi square further reveals that these identified problems among others significantly affect adult education in Nigeria;

Conclusion

Adult education's socio-economic development has a lot to render toward ensuring the desired development of the nation Nigeria, as shown in the Tables 6 and 7. It was also observed that literacy programmes have positive impact on the learners' socio-economic life. Thus, any efforts aimed at improving the Nigerian national development should consider adult education socio-economic programmes such as: Basic literacy on simple Arithmetic Women Empowerment Education, Vocational Education, Continuing-Professional Education, Training and Development, Labour Education, Workplace Learning, In-service Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Community Development Education, Health Education, Extension/Rural Development Education, Nomadic Education, Distance-Learning Education, Family-life Education, Retirement Education, Self Help/Self Reliance Education and Self Development Education.

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Lead City University Undergraduates Knowledge and Awareness of Health Campaigns on Prevention of Diabetes by Non-governmental Organisations

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Abstract

Diabetes is a metabolism disorder characterised by the presence of too much glucose in the blood leading to complications such as blindness or limb amputation. Diabetes remains the sixth leading cause of death in upper-middle-income countries. Hence, the study investigated Lead City University undergraduates' knowledge and awareness of health campaigns by Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs). The study adopted descriptive survey research design using questionnaire as the research instrument and sample involved 405 undergraduates of Lead City University, Ibadan, who were carefully selected through simple random sampling technique. The study was guided by the Health Belief Model and the Two-Step flow Theory. Differential and inferential statistics was used to analyse the data. The finding revealed that the students had knowledge of diabetes and the various platforms used for campaigns; there was joint and significant influence of knowledge towards the prevention of diabetes (Adjusted R² = 3; p<0.05; p<0.05) respectively. It was revealed that level of awareness significantly influenced knowledge towards the prevention of diabetes (Adjusted R² =.166;p < 0.05);again, health media campaign awareness was found to have significantly influenced knowledge towards the prevention of diabetes(Adjusted R² =.166;p<0.05). The study recommended that the federal, state, local governments and Non-Governmental Organizations should be more aggressive in disseminating information on the dangers of diabetes and how to prevent diabetes.

Keywords: Knowledge; Health Campaign; Awareness; Prevention; Diabetes; Undergraduates.

Word Count: 213

Introduction

According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), diabetes, is a condition resulting from abnormal chemical reactions in the human body characterised by the presence of too much glucose in the blood (hyperglycemia) as a result of defects in insulin (insulin regulates the metabolism of carbohydrates, fats and proteins) secretion, insulin action, or both. These abnormal reactions can lead to long-term damage, dysfunction and or failure of different organs (WHO, 2021). Diabetes Mellitus (DM) may appear with different symptoms such as thirst, polyuria, (frequent passing of urine) blurring of vision and weight loss.

The long-term effects of Diabetes Mellitus may include, retinopathy, a complication of diabetes that affects the eyes, which can lead to blindness, renal failure which occurs when the kidneys are not able to remove waste and balance body fluids, neuropathy where the nerves in the hands feet or arms are destroyed, foot ulcers and the risk of amputation of limbs. Other complications include charcot joints, a disorder that produces abnormal pain sensation and sexual or organ dysfunction.

When the condition degenerates, the body may produce excessive acids or ketones leading to ketoacidosis. People Living with Diabetes can also suffer from heart conditions where blood vessels are diseased and blood clots may develop (cardiovascular conditions). Other pathogenic processes have also been linked to the development of Diabetes (Yau, 2019). Such processes are responsible for the destruction of beta cells that produce insulin, the hormone that ensures that the glucose in the body does not become too high. The abnormalities in the metabolism of carbohydrate, fat and protein arise as a result of deficiency in the action of insulin on some tissues due to insensitivity of these cells to insulin or because the production of insulin has stopped. In children the diagnosis is usually confirmed through blood glucose measurements and treatment should be started immediately because it is a life threatening condition.

Some adolescents and a small number of children may not have severe symptoms, but may require fasting blood sugar measurements or Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT) for diagnosis (Yau,2019).The disease usually progress from high blood glucose levels (hyperglycaemia) to full blown diabetes due to deficiency of insulin secretion, insulin action

or both. There are two main types of diabetes, Type 1 Diabetes where the production of insulin from the pancreas dwindles or even ceases altogether. In Type 2 Diabetes, the cells of the body do not recognise the insulin produced and so develop insulin resistance (Ortelli, 2021; Kubota, 2017). Both types of diabetes are characterised by too much sugar in the blood (hyperglycaemia)

Gestational Diabetes is another type of diabetes which occurs in pregnant women without a previous history of diabetes, but suddenly develops high glucose levels. The condition occurs as a result of disturbance of the action of insulin perhaps by a hormone produced by the placenta and usually occurs around the 24th week of pregnancy. It has been observed that Gestational Diabetes (GDM) sufferers do not show the usual symptoms of Diabetes Mellitus and has been linked with the risk of obesity and abnormal glucose tolerance in childhood and adult life in the offspring (John, 2020).

Research has shown that there is an increase in the prevalence of diabetes worldwide and also that Type 2 Diabetes is more prevalent affecting 90% of all diagnosed diabetics around the world. Diabetes has become a worldwide pandemic and one of the major causes of premature illness and premature deaths (Ortelli, 2021). The World Health Organization has predicted that the number of adults living with diabetes will increase from 135 million in 1995 to 380 million in 2025 (WHO, 2021). The larger proportion of this increase will be as result of its health complications, the global-health related costs of diabetes are expected to rise and the highest percentage of the increase will occur in the developing world (WHO, 2021). This could be the result of rapid populations that are ageing, physical inactivity, consumption of energy dense foods and the adoption of western lifestyles and urbanisation (Kubota, 2017). The World Health Organization in its report stated that 1.71 million people are currently living with diabetes in Nigeria. Similarly, the 2011 International Diabetes Federation report stated that 3 Million Nigerians are living with diabetes and this figure is expected to rise to 4.84 million by 2030 (WHO, 2021).

The global prevalence of diabetes is almost 9%.2, and 90% of patients have Type 2 Diabetes. In addition, the prevalence of Gestational Diabetes (a type of diabetes that affects pregnant women) is on the increase with about 16% of all live births being diagnosed with

hyperglycaemia (Gandevani,2019).As a result of its health implications, the global health-related costs of diabetes are expected to rise from US\$1.3 trillion in 2015 to US 2.5 trillion by 2030,if past trends continue(Bommer,2018).This amounts to an increase in costs, globally from1.8% in 2015 to the very high level of 2.25 in 2030 (Bomer, 2018).

One of the problems of diabetes is that it is often undiagnosed. Research from across sub Saharan Africa concludes that diabetes is under-diagnosed. For example in a Cameroon study 60% of diabetic cases were discovered to be undiagnosed (IDF, 2020).In Ghana the figure was70% .in Tanzania, the figure was over 80%. (WDF, 2017; 2020). An equally serious problem is that diabetes in Children can be wrongly diagnosed, as is often done, as some other condition such as pneumonia or asthma (laboured breathing) as appendicitis or gastroenteritis (abdominal pain, vomiting),or as a serious infection such as malaria, typhoid, HIV/AIDS ,tuberculosis, meningitis, malnutrition or urinary tract infection.(Dessie,2020).

Another problem has to do with poor access to clinics, non-availability of drugs, unaffordable cost of treatment and care, dearth of trained staff with experience in diabetes care, and unavailability of equipment (Mercer, 2019). This situation has led diabetics in sub-Saharan Africa to patronise alternative health care providers such as traditional healers and/or herbalists (Hughes, 2015; Ayele,2 017).In addition research has shown that people in the lowest percentile of socioeconomic groups are 2.5 times more likely to come down with diabetes and that black and minority ethnic groups are six times more likely to develop diabetes when compared to the general population(Krayrou,2015,Bird,2015).

However, such groups are even more difficult to reach with preventive messages. Such preventive messages are communicated through health communication campaigns which promote health through the dissemination and absorption of messages via mass media, interpersonal channels and events. Health communication campaign can therefore be defined as the form of communication disseminated by the mass media for adequate health care delivery (Akinfeleye, 1989). Health campaigns could also include other activities such as clinician-patient interactions, classes, self-help groups, mailings and hot lines.

Several studies have shown that Diabetes Mellitus can be prevented or delayed, if intensive lifestyle changes are adopted by the people concerned, especially those living with pre-diabetes (Krayrou,2021,Mutyambizi, 2015). Several cases of diabetes mellitus could be prevented if people maintain healthy body weight, consume healthy diet and become more physically active. (NDPP, 2012-2019).

The theoretical framework for this study is guided by the Health Belief Model and the Two Step Flow Theory. The Health Belief Model was developed in the 1950's by a group of US public Health Service Social psychologists. It has six constructs viz.: perceived susceptibility, which is an individual's opinion regarding his/her chance of developing an illness. Perceived Severity, that is an individual's opinion of the severity of the disease if he/she contracts it; perceived benefits or what the individual stands to gain if he/she changes behavior to encourage better health status; perceived barriers or what are those obstacles standing in the way of the adoption of healthy behaviours; Cues to action is one of the constructs that enable individuals take actions consistent with their intentions.

Finally self-efficacy explains an individual's belief in his ability to perform efficiently as regards healthy behaviours. The Two-Step Flow Theory was propounded by Paul Lazarfeld, Bernard Berelson and Hazel Gaudet in 1940. The Two Step Flow Theory proposes that most individuals form their opinions based on the influence of opinion leaders. The Health belief model is relevant to this study because it examines steps taken by an individual before accepting a concept or adopting a behaviour. This is important because diabetes is one of the diseases where the individual takes a greater responsibility for treatment of his/her condition than the health care providers. Therefore if he/she does not believe in his/her ability, then things can quickly go from bad to worse. The Two Step Flow Theory highlights the importance and influence of opinion leaders, friends and family in the successful management of diabetes mellitus.

Statement of the Problem

Diabetes Mellitus is known to be a chronic disease that affects the survival growth and development of the human race. It is one of the most common chronic diseases in almost all the countries of the world and continues to increase numerically and significantly, as

changing lifestyles result in reduced physical activity and increase in obesity. As a result of this understanding, many campaigns by governments and non-governmental organizations have been carried out to emphasise the prevalence and the seriousness of diabetes.

Many of these campaigns are designed to create awareness and deepen the knowledge of people on diabetes, its characteristics, severity, complications and how it can be prevented or delayed.

However, it appears there is insufficient knowledge among the youths about diabetes prevention. This may have aggravated the rise in the number of cases in almost every country in the world. This is alarming and if not addressed could spiral into a pandemic that will derail the world's health care system. It is against this backdrop that this study is on the undergraduates of Lead City University knowledge of and awareness of health campaigns on prevention of diabetes by Non-Governmental Organisations.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to determine the Lead City University undergraduates' knowledge of health campaigns on prevention of diabetes by Non-Governmental Organisations. The specific objectives are to:

1. ascertain the level of knowledge of Lead City undergraduates on the existence of diabetes.
2. find out the level of knowledge of Lead City University undergraduates' on various campaigns on the prevention of diabetes.
3. ascertain the level of knowledge of Lead City University undergraduates' knowledge on various campaign platforms used for campaigns on prevention of diabetes.

Research Questions

The objectives of this study led to the following research questions which guided the study.

1. What is the level of knowledge of Lead City University undergraduates on the existence of diabetes?
2. What is the level of knowledge of Lead City University undergraduates on various campaigns by Non-Governmental Organisations on prevention of diabetes?
3. What is the level of knowledge of Lead City University undergraduates on the various platforms used by Non-Governmental Organisations for campaigns for prevention of diabetes?

Methodology

The study made use of survey research design. The study population comprised all the undergraduates of Lead City University,(5706 students).However, the sample size that was used was 405 undergraduates as presented in table1.The instrument used for the collection of data was the questionnaire self-constructed by the researchers.

Results of the study are presented below:

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (N 388)

Characteristics	Information	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	88	22.7
	Female	300	77.3
Age	16-20 years	79	20.4
	21-25 years	193	49.7
	26-30 years	49	12.6
	31-35 years	22	5.7
	36-40 years	18	4.6
	41 and above	27	7.0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 1, reveals that 300 of the respondents were female. This may imply that undergraduates in Universities in Nigeria are dominated by the female gender. The study revealed that majority of respondents are within the age range of 21-25 years (49.7%). This means that they are young, very much active, and still have a lot to learn as they focus on their careers. Those were within the age bracket of 21-25 years were 193, that is 49.7%, this is the largest number among the respondents. This may represent the age bracket of the largest number of students in Nigeria.

Those within the age range of 26-30 are 49, that is 12.6%, while those between the ages of 31-35 years are 22 or 5.7%. In the age range of 36-40 years 27 or 4.6% respondents participated in the study. It is to be noted that those respondents that were 41 and above were 27 in number. The study could not determine why this was so and may be the subject of future research.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Research Question One: What is the level of Knowledge of Lead City University undergraduates on the existence of diabetes?

Table 2: Level of knowledge on Existence of Diabetes (N 388)

Statement	HK (%)	K (%)	NTK (%)	NK (%)	Mean	SD	AM
1. I am aware of a disease known as diabetes.	312 (80.4)	76 (19.6)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3.80	0.397	3.30
2. I am aware of the existence of diabetes in my family.	96 (24.7)	79 (20.4)	76 (19.6)	137 (35.3)	2.35	1.196	
3. I am aware that diabetes can be well managed if detected early.	266 (68.6)	117 (30.2)	5 (1.3)	0 (0.0)	3.67	0.497	
4. I am aware that contracting diabetes is not a death sentence.	244 (62.9)	119 (30.7)	24 (6.2)	1 (0.3)	3.56	0.622	
5. I am well informed about the various causes and preventive techniques of diabetes.	157 (40.5)	122 (31.4)	107 (27.6)	2 (0.5)	3.12	0.83	0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Key: HK =Highly Knowledgeable, K= Knowledgeable, NTK- Not too Knowledgeable , NK = Not Knowledgeable at all, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean

It can be deduced from Table 2 that the level of knowledge on the existence of diabetes is moderate. This is reflected in the overall mean score of 2.50 on a four point scale on the level of knowledge of the disease called diabetes. This result suggests that more should be done by Non-Governmental agencies to increase knowledge of the existence of diabetes by youths through more aggressive campaigns.

Research Question Two: What is the Level of knowledge of Lead City University undergraduates of various media campaigns against diabetes?

Table 4.3: Level of knowledge of Lead City University undergraduates of various campaigns by Non-Governmental organisations on prevention of diabetes

Statement	HK (%)	K (%)	NTK (%)	NK (%)	Mean	S D	A M
1. I am aware of the existence of World diabetes day	138 (35.6)	101 (26.0)	77 (19.8)	72 (18.6)	2.79	1.1 20	2.50
2. I am aware of the existence of the campaigns on diabetes by Diabetes Association of Nigeria	119 (30.7)	97 (25.0)	108 (27.8)	64 (16.5)	2.70	1.0 76	
3. I am aware of the existence of the campaigns on diabetes by American Diabetes Association	73 (18.8)	87 (22.4)	126 (32.5)	102 (26.3)	2.34	1.0 62	
4. I am aware of the existence of the campaigns on diabetes by Rotary Club International	68 (17.5)	65 (16.8)	159 (41.0)	96 (24.7)	2.27	1.0 22	
5. I am aware of the existence of the campaigns on diabetes by the Federal, State and Local Governments of my Country	76 (19.6)	100 (25.8)	124 (32.0)	88 (22.7)	2.4	1.0 2 4 5	

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Key: HK =Highly Knowledgeable, K= Knowledgeable, NTK- Not too Knowledgeable, NK =Not Knowledgeable at all, M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean

Going by the knowledge of health campaigns by non-Governmental Organisations on prevention of diabetes on Table 2, it shows the average mean score of 2.50 on a four-point scale. It can be inferred that students are not so knowledgeable when it comes to campaigns by Non-Governmental Organisations. In fact they were not so knowledgeable about campaigns by Federal, State, and Local Governments in Nigeria.

Research Question Three: What is the level of knowledge of Lead City University undergraduates on various platforms used for campaigns for the prevention of diabetes?

Table 3: Level of Knowledge of Lead City University undergraduates of Various Platforms used by NGO on Campaigns for the Prevention of Diabetes

Statement	HK (%)	K (%)	NTK (%)	NK (%)	Mean	SD	A M
1. I am aware of a disease known as diabetes through leaflets and handbills	146 (37.6)	133 (34.3)	61 (15.7)	48 (12.4)	2.97	1.01 5	2.50
2. I am aware of the existence of a disease known as diabetes through the mass media (radio, television, and print media)	204 (52.6)	132 (34.0)	37 (9.5)	15 (3.9)	3.35	0.80 8	
3. I am aware of the existence of a disease known as diabetes through social media	191 (49.2)	130 (33.5)	39 (10.1)	28 (7.2)	3.25	0.90 7	
4. I am aware of the existence of a disease known as diabetes through bill boards International	104 (26.8)	108 (27.8)	116 (29.9)	60 (15.5)	2.66	1.03 6	
5. I am aware of the existence of a disease known as diabetes through families and friends	186 (47.9)	117 (30.2)	48 (12.5)	37 (9.5)	3.16	0.98 0	

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Key: HK =Highly Knowledgeable, K=Knowledgeable , NTK- Not too Knowledgeable, NK = Not knowledgeable at all. M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean.

The level of Knowledge, on various platforms, used for campaigns by Non-Governmental Organisations on diabetes is high on a scale of four points. It can be deduced from the mean score of 3.08. This shows that platforms such as mass media and social media, used by Non-Governmental Organisations have helped people, to get along with many things happening around the globe. The ability of people, especially undergraduates, to become more knowledgeable via social and mass media is on the high side. This is a vital platform to increase any form of awareness and knowledge. The social media is easily accessible and acceptable by youths and would be an ideal tool to enhance information delivery on diabetes prevention. The study has established that Non-Governmental Organisations are alive to their responsibilities in terms of campaigns to prevent diabetes. However much more needs to be done. Diabetes is a mass killer and cannot and should not be treated with kid gloves. A lot is being done but a lot more can still be done.

Conclusion

The study concludes that Diabetes Mellitus is an epidemic that has actually become a pandemic all over the world. It has identified Diabetes Mellitus as a chronic metabolism disease that attacks both young and old. However, there is a ray of hope if one has information and knowledge, diabetes can be prevented or delayed.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby given for this study:

1. Non-Governmental Organisations should change their campaign strategies and become more aggressive in order to create more awareness and knowledge on the dangers of diabetes mellitus and strive to reach more families.
2. Non-Governmental Organisations should come together under an umbrella for the purpose of promoting diabetes knowledge among young people. Funds should be allocated for this purpose so that diabetes will not hinder the next generation from achieving their set goals in life.
3. Therefore Non-Governmental Organisations should join hands with Governments to ensure that diabetes does not wipe off the existence of the human race.

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Impact of Media Campaign on Female Students' Knowledge and Perception of Early Marriage and Its Associated Health Risks in Minna Metropolis, Northern Nigeria

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Abstract

Early marriage is a socio-cultural practice among Africans and particularly in Nigeria that denies the girl-child the rights to choice of marriage. Globally, early marriage is regarded as an illegal adult male union with a minor, violating the rights of the girl-child. Despite international agreements and conventions, the practice is still prevalent in Northern Nigeria. Therefore, this study investigated the impact of health media campaign on early marriage knowledge, perception and its health risks among female students in Minna, Niger State. The study adopted one group pretest-posttest experimental design. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 195 female students from a government secondary school in Minna Metropolis. Two Instruments were used for data gathering i.e. Impact of Health Media Campaign Questionnaire (IHMCQ) $r=0.76$, Early Marriage Health Risks Achievement Test (EMHRAT) $r=0.72$; three intervention materials alongside video preview of the Movie 'Dry'. Findings revealed that combined health media campaign on early marriage had positive impact on female students' perception about early marriage and early marriage health risks. There is significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of female students' knowledge of early marriage as well as significant difference in their perception of early marriage based on age [$f(3, 193) = 3.059$; $P < 0.05$]. But no significant difference in the female students' knowledge of early marriage based on; religion [$f(1, 195) = 2.437$; $P > 0.05$]; Class [$f(2, 194) = 0.230$; $P > 0.05$]; and Ethnicity [$f(9, 187) = 0.230$; $P > 0.05$]. This implies that age is a factor and major determinant in the knowledge of early marriage across the age group. The study recommends the implementation of the child right law in all 36 states in Nigeria and advocate for the involvement of religions leaders to reduce the practice.

Keywords: Impact, Media Campaign, Knowledge, Perception, Early Marriage, Health risks.

Word Count: 295

Introduction

Early marriage is not just a Nigeria or Africa issue but a global phenomenon that depict the adolescent girl as a lower citizen in most part of the world. Early marriages are carried out before the girl is physically, physiologically, emotionally and psychologically ready to shoulder the responsibilities of marriage and childbearing. Thus early marriage has major consequences on the girl's health, national security, social development, human right, economic development and gender equality (Walker, Mukisa, Hashim, & Ismail, 2013). Early marriage is highly prevalent in some part of the world for some reasons including poverty, war, religion, traditional believes, insecurity and family honour. The practice of early marriage is common in Africa, South Asia, Southeast Asia, West Asia, Latin America and Oceania. Early marriage often compromises a girl's development by resulting in early pregnancy, social isolation, interrupted schooling, limited opportunities for career and vocational advancement.

The resultant effect of the extreme poverty in Northern Nigeria is overwhelming with 77.7% in the North-West and 76.3% in the north –East (National Bureau of Statistic [NBS], 2010). This makes daughters economic burden to the family and is often relieved by early marriage. Poor parents see marriage as the best option to ensure their daughter's financial security and reduce the economic burden of a growing adult in the family by giving their daughters out to rich suitors, the economic status of the family is elevated by the in-laws who shower them with financial gains and gift. This is highly accepted and considered as best for the girl's welfare. Girls from poor homes hold an average age of marrying at 15years while girls from wealthy homes marry at an average age of 23yaers. Ignorance is another factor that plays a major role in early marriage, as most parents are unaware of the consequences and health complications that arise from the practice of early marriage. Girls who are unfortunate to contract obstetrics fistulas are tagged weak and ostracize form the community or even band from communicating with anyone in the community.

The most vulnerable people in the world are women and girls, especially the uneducated once. Educational attainment is a strong indicator whether a girl will marry as a child or not. According to United Nation Educational Scientific Culture (UNESCO), Nigeria holds the world record with the most children out of school with approximately 10.5millions. 82% of women with no education were married before 18, as opposed to 13%

of women who had at least finished secondary education (UNESCO 2015). In Northern region, parents have complained that the quality of education is so poor that schooling cannot be considered a viable alternative to marriage for their daughters (UNICEF, 2016). Over the past decades findings has showed that young wives usually quit school in other to be caregivers of their new family.

Furthermore, religion and traditional believes fluids early marriage, that makes the issues of early marriage very delicate to Nigeria. A country split down the middle between religious lines, makes the issues to be considered a very sensitive one. To some extent Islam contributes to early marriage because Shariat Law is based in part on the life of Muhammad, the prophet, as described in part Sahih Bukhari and Sahih Muslim. Muhammad married Aisha, his third wife when she was six (6) years old Denise (1996) and consummated the marriage when she was about 9years of age. Some mainstream Islamic scholars have suggested that it not the chronological age that matters; marriageable age under the Muslims religion law is when the guardian of the girl feels she has reach sexual maturity and such determination of sexual maturity is a matter of subjectivity judgement (Denise, 1996).

Although marriage is not mentioned directly in the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), early marriage is linked to other rights such as the right to freedom of expression, the right to protection from all forms of abuse, and the right to be protected from harmful traditional practices. All issues relating to a child's right are frequently addressed by the Committee on the Rights of the Child. Other International agreements related to child marriage are the Convention on Consent to Marriage (CCM), Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages (MAMRM), the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (ACRWC) and the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and People's Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (UNICEF Global Database 2016).

Early marriage poses great threat on the health of girls, the health risk factors and hazard are extremely alarming and one that call for urgent attention. Most of the young brides experience complication during pregnancy and child birth because the pelvic is not fully developed for child bearing also young brides under 18 years of age are more likely to suffer from Vesico Vagina Fistula, Maternal Mortality and Neonatal mortality, Obstetric Palsy, Cancer of the Pelvis, Recto Vagina Fistula, wide spread of Human Immune Deficiency Virus (HIV) Acquired Immune Deficiency Virus (AIDS) and other transmitted sexual diseases and infections.

The term health communication was developed in an International Communication Association (ICA) interest group meeting. Health communication is an interdisciplinary field, the relationship between health and communication existed long before the term "health communication" was introduced (Stacks & Salween, 2015). The research in health communication surrounds the development of effective's messages about health, the dissemination of health-related information through broadcast, print, and electronic media, and the role of inter personal relationships in health communities. At the core of all of the communication are the idea of health and the emphasis of health. The goal of health communication research is to identify and provide better and more effective communication strategies that will improve the overall health of the society (Stacks & Salween, 2015).

Health communication is the study and practice of communicating and promotion of health information; such as public health campaign, health education and between doctor and patient. National Communication Association (NCA) observes that the purpose for disseminating health information is to influence personal health choices by improving health literacy because effective health communication must be tailored for the audience and the situation. Health Communication seeks to:

1. Create audience knowledge and awareness of a health issue (Gwyn, 2002).
2. Influence behaviour and attitude toward a health issue.
3. Demonstrate health practices
4. Demonstrates the benefit behaviour changes to public outcome
5. Advocate a position on a health issue or policy (Freimuth and Quinn, 2004.)
6. Increase demand or support for health services
7. Argue against misconception about health.(National Communication Association, 2013)

There are many reasons why health communication research is important, one of which is how it betters the health care field and it numerous service to the entire society. Thus, communication in health can be defined as the symbolic exchange of shared meaning and all communicative acts have both a transmission and a ritualistic component. Intervention efforts to change behaviour are also regarded as communicative acts. By focusing mostly on the transmission function of information exchange, such efforts often neglect ritualistic processes that are automatically engaged through communication. In adopting the transmission view of

communication, it is reasonable to think carefully about the channels through which intervention messages are disseminated, to whom the message is attributed; how audience members respond and the features of messages that have the greatest impact (World Health Organization, 2010).

These considerations reflect the essential components of the communication process i.e. channel, source, receiver and message, respectively (Otunla, 2014). Strategies for tailoring health messages are one major component for persuasive health communication. (Noar, Christina, Banac, Melissa & Harris 2007). To ensure that messages of health communication reach selected audiences accurately and quickly, health communication professionals must assemble a collection of superior and audience appropriate information that target population segments (Noar, et.al; 2007). Understanding the audience for the information is also critical to effective delivery of the message. Communication is an activity that involves oral speech, voice, tone, nonverbal body language, listening and more. Communication is also a process for a mutual understanding that occurs during interpersonal communication in the class room, within the clinic and at some other places (Otunla, 2014).

The history of health campaign can be traced back to the 19th century in America when the Women's Christian Temperance Union led a movement against alcohol abuse (HCB, 2013). The union utilized the mass media to communicate the desired messages. Newspapers and magazines were used for the promotion of the anti-alcohol movement. In 1721 at Boston health communication was used by Cotton Mather to mitigate the smallpox epidemic in Boston. Mather a political leader used pamphlets and health` speeches to promote inoculation of smallpox. Thus health Communication campaigns are arguably the most utilized and effective method for spreading Public Health messages, especially in endorsing disease prevention.

According to a study by United Nation International Children Education Fund (UNICEF, 2016) the rate of early marriage are highest in Sub-Sahara Africa countries, where around 4in10 girls marry before age 18. About 1 in 18 were married or in union before 15. Followed by Latin America, the Caribbean, Middle East, and North Africa were 24% and 18% respectively. United Nation for Population Activities (UNFPA, 2014) give an account that Nigerian women between the ages of twenty and twenty-four, 76% reported marrying before the age of 18 and 28% reported marrying before the age of fifteen.

In Asia and Africa the importance of financial transaction at weddings also tends to push family to marry their daughter early. For families in many Sub-Sahara countries parents get a high price for a daughter who is married near puberty as an avenue to sustain her virginity and family honour. Another account by UNFPA indicated that in many Sub-Saharan countries, there is a high incidence of marriage among girls younger than 15. Africa governments have tended to overlook the problems resulting from child marriage, including obstetric fistulae, premature births, stillbirth, sexually transmitted diseases (including cervical cancer), and malaria. Nigeria attempted to change Section 29, subsection 4 of the 1999 constitution and thereby prohibit child marriages.

Christianity and Islam are practiced by roughly 50%-50% of its population respectively where child marriages is forbidden for Christians and allowed by Muslims. Child marriage is a divisive topic in Nigeria and widely practiced in the Northern states, predominantly Muslim, over 50% of the girls marry before the age of 15. The scourge of early marriage in Nigeria has being one of great concerned and still is, according to Girls not Bride, early marriage is predominantly practiced in the Northern part of Nigeria with a percentage as high as 76% in the North West Region and as low as 10% in the south East. Thus, early marriage is predominant in Northern Nigeria as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Age of Early Marriage by Location in Nigeria (Data source: Estimation from the Nigeria Demography and Health Survey (NDHS 2008))

Region	No of Observation	Age of First Marriage	
		Median	Mean
North Central	5630	17	18
North East	5467	15	15.8
North West	6582	15	15.4
South East	3201	20	21
South West	4184	19	19.5
South South	4366	20	20.7

Source: Estimation from the Nigeria Demography and Health Survey (NDHS 2008).

The summary from the table reveals that girls mostly from Northern Nigeria are likely to marry at age 15 as against her counterpart who marry at age 20 in other part of the country, especially in the south. Furthering of education and other vocational skills are almost

impossible for many girls who have to depend on their husbands for everything almost for the rest of their lives, thereby crippling the growth and economy of the nation.

In another account, Gambi and Joseph (2014) reported that in the pre-independence era when formal education was first introduced in Northern Nigeria, the government through the Native Authority (NA); that later transformed to Local Government Councils had to force parents to send their daughters to school. To ensure compliance Native Authorities fully funded the education of the girls who were conscripted to various schools often located outside their province. However, the socio-cultural and religious practices that evolved later in the Northern Nigeria, particularly the present states located in the North East and North West changed with the highest number of adolescent girls not enrolled in schools and those who drop out to get married. In a recent survey, Nigeria is regarded as having one of highest cases of early marriage in the world UNFPA (2017). The Child Rights Act passed in 2003, raised the minimum age of marriage to 18 years for girls.

However, Federal law may be implemented differently at the state level and to date only twenty-three states has taken concrete step to implement the minimum age of marriage to 18 years of age. To further complicate matters, Nigeria has three different legal systems operating simultaneously they are: civil law, customary law, and Islamic law of which the State and Federal governments have control only over marriages that take place within the civil system of government (Sulaiman, 2008).

It is almost certain that most of the early marriages are conducted traditionally or religiously which makes it difficult to legislate over when adolescent girls are already married. Majority of the girls never return to school to complete their education, not likely to learn a trade or acquire vocational skills that would economically empower and make them self-reliant (Adekola, Akanbi & Olawole, 2015). Every society and culture has some basic norms and beliefs that guide the people (Gimba & Joseph, 2014). Early marriage has been identified as one of the main causes of obstetric fistulas In Nigeria, it is the most devastating of all pregnancy related disabilities and Nigeria account for 40% of fistulas cases in the world (UNFPA, 2017).

Most of the adolescent girls are married too young before they gain maturity physically, go through a lot of health challenges which effects them physical and mentally. Without support from the Government and some International Organisation some of these adolescents girls lose their life as they are ostracize from the society and abandon by their

husbands and family who considered them weak or witches. The health effect of early marriage which is consider most hazardous to the life's of the adolescent girls include Obstetric Fistula, Obstetric Palsy, Maternal Mortality, Infant Mortality, Sexual Transmitted Infections, Cervical Cancer, HIV/AIDS, Sexual Transmitted Disease.

Table 2: Estimates for Regional, Urban and Rural Differences in the Maternal Mortality Ratio, Nigeria.

Location	Region/ Geo-Political Zone	Maternal Death Per Live Birth
Geo-Political Location	North- East	1,549
	South West	165
Social-Economic Location	Urban	828
	Rural	351

Source :(FMH,2011,2015, WHO,2014)

Consequently, from the information in Table 2; pregnancy-related complications are the leading cause of death among young women aged 15-19 years. Adolescent mothers are at particular risk for maternal conditions such as anaemia, obstructed labour and fistula. They are also less likely to use skilled maternal health services than mothers 20 years and above. About one-third of 15-19 year-olds in Northern Nigeria have delivered a child without the help of a health professional, a traditional birth attendant, or even a friend or relative. While there is evidence that the use of skilled maternity care is growing, unattended home deliveries are widespread, consistently averaging 60% of all deliveries in Nigeria since the 1990s. Less than half of women attend the recommended four or more prenatal care visits when pregnant. Only a third of women seek the recommended care during the postnatal period, a proportion that has remained low over the past decades.

Some of the barriers to seeking optimal maternity care include cost of services, distance to health facilities, harmful cultural practices and believe, long waiting times for those seeking care at public health facilities. Abuse and mistreatment of care-seekers by health care providers at public health facilities. Nigeria joined the Africa Union Campaign to

end early marriage in November 2016. The Vice President Prof. Yemi Osinbajo officially launched a nation-wide campaign to end early marriage, making Nigeria the 16th country to join the Africa Union campaign.

The Federal Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Development together with partners UNFPA, UNICEF and Save the Children, developed the campaign in line with the Sustainable Development Goals that Nigeria has committed to achieve in 2030 (UNICEF Nigeria, 2016). If early marriage of adolescent girls will be swept out of our nation we must first as a nation address the root problem, eliminate them, adopt, develop, and strictly implement policies that will enhance the advancement of the adolescent girls in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

A number of socio-cultural practices deny women and girls their rights to social development in homes and the society. One of such practices is early marriage of girls. Despite International Agreements, legislation, conventions and policies early marriage among young adolescent girls is widely practiced. Somewhere around the world, it is presumed that about thirty girls every minute are married off too soon before the age of eighteen years. Early marriage or child marriage has posed great dangers in the lives of the adolescent girls for decades because of the health risk factors involved. Additionally from literature, no fewer than 800,000 girls have suffered from obstetric fistulas such as Vesico Vaginal Fistula and Recto Vaginal Fistula, Neonatal Mortality and Maternal Mortality due to inadequate health provision, marrying too early and getting pregnancy too early. This study therefore investigated the impact of media campaign on female students' knowledge and perception of early marriage health risks in Minna metropolis in Northern Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to determine the effect of media health campaign on female students' knowledge and perception of early marriage and its health risks. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. ascertain female students' perception of early marriage health risks and
2. find out the perceived impact of the health media campaign on early marriage health risks.

3. determine the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of female students' knowledge of early marriage
4. determine the significant difference in the senior secondary school students' knowledge of early marriage in Minna metropolis based on religion,
5. determine the significant difference in the female students' knowledge of early marriage based on age, class and ethnicity

Research Questions

One research question was raised and three research hypotheses were tested in the study as follows:

1. What is the perceived impact of the health media campaign on early marriage and its risks?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of female students' knowledge of early marriage.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the senior secondary school students' knowledge of early marriage in Minna metropolis based on religion.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the female students' knowledge of early marriage based on age, class and ethnicity.

Methodology

Research Design: The study adopted one group pretest-posttest quasi experimental design. The design was adopted to evaluate the impact of the intervention i.e. the health media campaign conducted among the participants. However, the research was conducted in stages: Stage one featured baseline assessment of female students' knowledge and perception of early marriage health risks; while stage two involved conduct of the intervention through health talk, poster presentation and preview of the movie 'Dry' shortly after the administration of pre-test.

Thereafter, impact assessment of the health media campaign was administered to test for knowledge and perception of early marriage health risks using post-test.

Population of the Study: The population for the study involve all female students of Government Secondary School, Old Airport, Bosso local Government, Niger State. North-Central, Nigeria.

Sampling Technique and Sample: Purposive sampling technique was used to select Government Secondary School, Old Airport, Bosso Local Government Area, Minna Metropolis because students in the intact classes are required. Random sampling technique was used to select female students from SS two (2) to SS three (3).

Research Instruments: Two Instruments and three intervention materials were used; they are:

1. Perceived Impact of Health Media Campaign Questionnaire (IHMCQ)
2. Early Marriage Health Risks Achievement Test (EMHRAT)
3. Health Communication Graphics Materials (HCGM)
4. Instructional Guide on 'Early Marriage Health Risks'
5. Video Presentation of the Movie 'Dry'

Reliability of the Instruments: The reliability values for the instruments were considered adequate for the study. Such that first instrument; Perceived Impact of Health Media Campaign Questionnaire (IHMCQ) yielded Cronbach Alpha of 0.76 while the second instrument; Early Marriage Health Risks Achievement Test (EMHRAT) recorded Richard Kuderson formula 21 (KR-21) 0.72.

Results and Discussion

The study involved a total sample of one hundred and ninety five (195) female senior secondary students of Government Secondary School, Old Airport including 63 SS two students and 132 SS 3 students. Demographic characteristics of the students is presented in Table 3

Table 3: Demographic Information of Respondents by Religion, Age, Ethnicity and Parents' Occupation (N=195)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Religion		
Christianity	32	17.8
Islam	162	82.2
Age		
13-14years	14	7.1
15-16years	48	24.4
17-18years	113	57.4
18years and above	22	11.2
Class		
SSS1	0	0
SSS2	65	32
SSS3	132	67
No response	2	1.0
Ethnicity		
Nupe	87	44.2
Gbagy	33	16.8
Koro	1	0.5
Tiv	4	2.0
Hausa	27	13.7
Igbo	8	4.1
Yoruba	30	15.2
Others	9	3.6
Father's Occupation		
Civil servant	103	52.6
Trader	7	3.6
Business Man	72	36.5
Others	15	7.6
Mother's Occupation		
Civil servant	46	23.4
Trader	33	16.8
Business Woman	106	53.8
Others	12	6.1

Source: Field Data (2018)

Table 3 presents the respondents' characteristics which indicated that 162 (82.2%) Muslims and 35 (17.8%) Christians in Minna Metropolis were involved in the study. Finding further revealed that majority i.e. 113 (57.4%) of the respondents are ages between 17-

18years; 48 (24.4%) are ages between 15-16years, 14 (7.1%) are of ages between 13-14years and 22 (11.2%) ages 19 years and above.

The table also indicated the class of the students with the majority; 132 (67%) of the students are in the senior secondary school III, while 63 (32%) are in the senior secondary school II while 2 (1%) of the responses are missing.

Respondents' Ethnic group shows that the majority 87 (44.2%) belong to the *Nupe* ethnic group, 33 (16.8%) *Gbagy*, 30 (15.2%) *Yorubas* and 27 (13.7%) are Hausas, 8 (4.1%) are Igbos, 4 (2%) are *Tivs* and 1 (0.5%) from *Koro* ethnic group. Lastly, father's occupation ranges from Civil servants 103 (52.6%) being the majority; while business men recorded 72 (36.5%), traders 7 (3.6%) and 15 (7.6%) for others. Mothers' occupation indicated that 46 (23.4%) were civil servants, 106 (53.8%); were into business, 33 (16.8%) were traders and others recorded 12 (6.1%).

Research Question One: what is the perceived impact of health media awareness campaign on early marriage among female students?

Table 4: Impact of Health Media Awareness Campaign on Early Marriage (N=195)

S/N	Impact of Health Media Awareness Campaign on Early Marriage	Highly	Minimal	Low	Mean	Std.Dev
1	I am well informed on issues of health risks in relation to early marriage	189 95.9%	6 3%	2 1%	2.94	0.30
2	Issues relating to sudden death of married school-age girls during child delivery is clear to me	178 90.4%	11 5.6%	8 4.1%	2.85	0.47
3	Issues relating to new born of married school-age girls during child delivery is clear to me	172 87.3%	21 10.7%	4 2%	2.84	0.43
4	I am now aware of domestic violence relating to early marriage	176 89.3%	20 10.2%	1 0.5%	2.88	0.33
5	My perception has change about early marriage	191 97%	5 2.5%	1 0.5%	2.95	0.26
6	My perception has change about early marriage health risks	175 88.8%	13 6.6%	9 4.6%	2.83	0.52
7	I am well informed that one of the consequences of babies delivered by married school-age girls are deprived of adequate care	175 88.8%	14 7.1%	8 4.1%	2.83	0.50
8	Married school-age girls are at risk of vesico virginal fistula VVF	173 87.8%	22 11.2%	2 1%	2.86	0.39
9	Married school-age girls are at risk of maternal mortality	170 86.3%	18 9.1%	9 4.6%	2.81	0.51
10	Most married school-age girls are at risk of adequate health care	171 86.8%	17 8.6%	9 4.6%	2.82	0.48
Grand mean = 2.86						

Source: Field Data (2018)

Table 4 shows the perceived impact of health media awareness campaign on early marriage among female students in Minna metropolis. The table indicated that 189(95.9%) of

the respondent are highly informed on issues of health risks in relation to early marriage as against 2 (1%) who lowly informed. 175 (88.8%) are highly informed that one of the consequences of babies delivered by married school-age girls are deprived of adequate care as against 8 (4.1%) who are lowly informed. Also, 178 (90.4%) are highly aware of issues relating to sudden death of married school-age girls during child delivery are clear to them and 191 (97%) has their perception changed about early marriage. Since the grand mean of 2.86, for all the items is greater than 2.50 cut off point; finding implies that health media campaign on early marriage had positive impact on female students' perception about early marriage and its health risks.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test score of female students' knowledge of early marriage in Minna metropolis.

Table 5: Mean Difference of Pre-Test and Post-Test Score of Students' Knowledge Early Marriage

Score	No	Mean	S.D.	T	Df	Sig	D
Pre	195	4.54	0.92	2.245	196	.026*	0.306
Post	195	4.37	0.821				
Total	195						

Source: Field Data (2018)

Table 5 shows the $t_{(196)} = 2.245$ is less than the p value ($p < 0.05$). Hence, there was significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of female students' knowledge of early marriage. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. The mean scores indicated that the pre-test score of knowledge of early marriage is higher than that of the post-test score and it is statistically significant.

However, the effect size of the timing of the test on students' knowledge about early marriage is 0.306, this implies that timing accounted for 30.6% of the total variance explained in students' knowledge about early marriage, and the remaining 69.4% are due to other factors outside timing.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the female students' knowledge of early marriage in Minna metropolis based on religion

Table 6: Mean Difference of Knowledge Students' Early Marriage based on Religion
ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.632	1	1.632	2.437	.120
Within Groups	130.571	195	.670		
Total	132.203	196			
Christian	4.57				
Muslim	4.33				

Source: Field Data (2018)

Table 6 shows that there was no significant difference in the female students' knowledge of early marriage based on religion [$f(1, 195) = 2.437; P > 0.05$]. This implies that irrespective of the respondents' religion, their knowledge of early marriage remain the same. This is further shown by the mean score i.e. Christian (4.57) and Muslim (4.33) which is not statistically significant.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the female students' knowledge of early marriage in Minna metropolis based on age, class and ethnicity.

Table 7: Mean Difference of Knowledge of Early Marriage based on Age

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	9.178	3	3.059	4.799	.003
Within Groups	123.025	193	.637		
Total	132.203	196			
13-14yrs				5.0000	
15-16yrs				4.5417	
17-18yrs				4.2301	
19yrs+				4.3636	

Mean Difference in Knowledge of Early Marriage based on Class

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.313	2	.157	.230	.795
Within Groups	131.890	194	.680		
Total	132.203	196			

Mean Difference of Knowledge Early Marriage Based on Ethnicity

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.638	9	.293	.423	.922
Within Groups	129.565	187	.693		
Total	132.203	196			

Source Field Data (2018)

Table 7 shows that there was a significant difference in the female students' perception of early marriage based on age [$f(3, 193) = 3.059; P < 0.05$]. It implies that age is a factor and major determinant in the knowledge of early marriage across the age group. This is further shown by students' mean score which is within age bracket 13-14 and has an highest mean score which is statistically different from 17-18 year age bracket which has the lowest mean score of 4.2. This is an indication that creating awareness among the vulnerable girls will go a long way to minimize the practice of early marriage. Students within age 13 and 14 years are likely to have become more knowledgeable of consequences of early marriage at an early age than their older counterparts. It also suffices to say that the health media campaign is impactful on students within ages 13 and 14 years.

There was no significant difference in the female students' knowledge of early marriage based on class [$f(2, 194) = 0.230; P > 0.05$]. This then means that irrespective of their class, their knowledge of early marriage remain the same. There was no significant difference in the female students' knowledge of early marriage based on Ethnicity [$f(9, 187) = 0.230; P > 0.05$]. In summary, findings revealed that there is no significant difference in students' knowledge of early marriage irrespective of their ethnic groups

Findings revealed that the health media campaign on early marriage had positive impact on female students' perception about early marriage and its health risks. There was significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of female students' knowledge of early marriage as well as significant difference in their perception of early marriage based on age [$f(3, 193) = 3.059; P < 0.05$]; which implies that age is a factor and major determinant in the knowledge of early marriage across the age group.

Further, finding revealed that there was no significant difference in the female students' knowledge of early marriage based on religion [$f(1, 195) = 2.437; P > 0.05$] and based on Class [$f(2, 194) = 0.230; P > 0.05$] and based on Ethnicity [$f(9, 187) = 0.230; P > 0.05$].

This finding is also in line with the UNICEF (2016) report because education changes and reshapes the knowledge and perception of adolescent on early marriage. Therefore female students as covered in this study are more knowledgeable about early marriage and the health risks because they are exposed to information and awareness programs like the health media

campaign conducted as part of the study which other adolescent girls who supposedly reside in rural areas are unlikely to be exposed to.

Finding further justifies the fact that some adolescent girls are beginning to make giant steps in relations to gender equality, an example is the story of a 16-year-old girl from Niger State who filed for a divorce after being forced by her family to marry against her wish and was supported by the Ministry of Women Affairs (Premium News, 2017).

Conclusion

From the study it is obvious that early marriage is still a practice and young adolescent girls should be informed of the social effect but as well be informed adequately of the health risks related to early marriage and early pregnancy. Although religion and poverty play a major role as drivers of early marriage in Nigeria, young adolescent girls are beginning to be aware of the consequence and are raising their voices to say no to this harmful practice. Thus, it will not be an oversight to say early marriage poses great health risks to the life and future of adolescent girls. It robs the nation of potentials, increases maternal mortality, neonatal mortality cripples the economy and increases the rate of poverty in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Arising from the findings of the study, the following recommendations are put forward:

1. The Nigeria government should make and strictly implement relevant legislation and conventions on early marriage.
2. The State governments should implement the Child Right Act in all 36 states of the country.
3. Government at various levels should involve the religious leaders especially; Islamic clerics for proper interpretation of the Quran on early marriage since it is widely practiced among Northern Muslims.

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Assessment of the Public Relations Strategies of Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (IBEDC) on Customer Satisfaction in Ibadan Metropolis**BABALEYE, Taye Ph.D**Department of Mass Communication and Media Technology,
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Abstract

Public relations strategies in this study are customer care, publicity, direct marketing, social media engagement, weekly sponsored programmes in the media, community engagement, SMS, corporate social responsibility, media relations, advertising, public campaign, promotion, and publicity. Customer satisfaction is the most reliable characteristic of customers' feedback, bearing in mind that it reflects their preferences. This study thus examined the assessment of Public relations strategies of Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (IBEDC) on Customers' satisfaction in Ibadan Metropolis. Two theories were adopted for the study and they are Stakeholder Theory and Situational theory. Descriptive survey research method was applied to gather data, and key informant interview was also used. A total of 353 copies of the questionnaire were administered on respondents who were customers of IBEDC in Ibadan Metropolis. Findings showed that majority of the respondents (70%) were fully aware of the public relations strategies used by IBEDC to enhance customers' satisfaction. The respondents further admitted that the usage of public relations strategies positively enhanced customers' satisfaction. It was discovered however that 55% of the respondents complained of poor power fluctuations. It is therefore recommended that IBEDC should improve its services to enhance its public relations strategies to support customers' satisfaction. Furthermore, it is also recommended that IBEDC should establish more public relations strategies to enable existing and potential customers make suggestions on how the firm's services could be improved.

Key Words: Public Relations Strategies, Customers' Satisfaction, Customer relations, Electricity, Distribution, Power Outage**Word Count:** 227

Introduction

The Public Relations Society of America (PRSA) asserts that public relations arose from the basic need of building and improving human relationship which existed immediately God created Adam and Eve. Thus, the concept of public relations (PR) has been with man. The creation of public relations between the creator and the creature both brought harmony and understanding in their relationship. Public Relations, however, existed during the days of John the Baptist in the Bible (Babaleye, 2021). Also, Moses who led the children of Israel out of slavery in Egypt was a stutter and needed someone who would convey his messages to the Israelites on his behalf. According to the bible, God chose Aaron, his brother to serve as the link between the Israelites and Moses. From the biblical perspective therefore, Aaron was a public relations officer for Moses (Babaleye, 2021).

Thus, Public Relations has been practiced, even if only amateurish, since the beginning of mankind. In ancient societies, human communication was limited by space and time. Due to the absence of modern technology, majority of the people lived simple lives in farms and small settlements. Communication flow, therefore in the olden days was primarily personal. The potentials and application of public relations increased as societies became more urbanized, civilized and complex. Modern public relations as a profession began in 1900s, when the first public relations agency, the Publicity Bureau was founded in the USA. Ivy Lee and Edward Bernays, who are both referred to as the founding fathers of modern Public Relations, helped establish the field as a professional practice in the United States. The profession became more established after World War II, in part due to talent from war-time publicity efforts moving into the private sector. Trade associations, industry publications and academic journals were developed. According to Grunig and Dozier (2015); Lashkin (2009), some of today's largest Public Relations agencies were founded in the 1950s and began competing globally in Europe and Asia in the beginning of the 60s and 70s.

The British colonial administrators established the first public relations department in Nigeria on 1st January, 1944, just a year before the end of the war in 1945. The first Public Relations (PR) department was established with the sole purpose of persuading Nigerians to continue to join the British army to prosecute the war to the end. Able bodied Nigerian men were drafted

to fight as British soldiers in North Africa and Asia especially in India, and Bombay, alongside other British colonial soldiers in a war we never knew anything about (Babaleye, 2021). The new PR department established in Nigeria was headed by Mr. D.C Fletcher who was the leader of a group of staff, which included a public relations officer, an assistant public relations officer, a process engraver, a press officer, a publicist, an artist, an antiquities officer, a photographer, a film officer, a radio officer and a confidential secretary. The function of the department was mainly to carry out “public enlightenment” programmes relating to government activities.

Public relations strategies are often used to help company organise its public relations (or media relations) activities and make strategic decisions about the best way to communicate with its target audience (Grunig and Dozier 2017). The development and implementation of public relations strategies can assist brands in not only generating interest from the press in their products or services but also to help promote product brands to resonate with their diverse audiences. If the strategy is implemented well, it will serve as a tool to help manage the public perception of an organisation. According to Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company, the public relations strategies used include advertising, public campaign, promotion, publicity, marketing, community engagement, town hall meetings, press conferences and writing press releases.

Measuring customer satisfaction is one of the most important issues regarding commercial organisations of all types. The philosophy of the client-focused approach of modern business organisations and implementation of the basic principles of continuous improvement justify the importance of measuring and analyzing the customer satisfaction (Kudeshia and Kumar, 2017). Currently, satisfaction is seen as the most reliable characteristic of customers’ feedback, bearing in mind that it reflects the preferences and expectations of the customers effectively, meaningfully and objectively (Kaur & Sarang, 2020). Today’s customer satisfaction can therefore be seen as a possible quality standard in commercial organisations. On the other hand, it is impossible to continuously motivate employees of a company by non-materials. For this reason, customers’ satisfaction must be in the range of measurable parameters directly related to benefits derived from organisations. It must become a factor,

which can be understood and influenced (Silva, Khan , Vorley & Zeng, 2011; Kaur & Sarang, 2020)

In today's corporate world, Public Relations related activities are geared towards the satisfaction of the publics. In the case of both public and private sectors, a poor customer image does not have any positive effect on the organisation's image in the eyes of stakeholders and consumers in general (Arinichev, Arinicheva , Mateeva & Damilova, 2019) In general, corporate image is considered an asset which gives the organisation a chance to differentiate itself, aiming to maximize their market share, profits, attracting new customers, retaining existing ones, neutralizing the competitors' actions and above all, their success and survival in the market (Zeng and Wu, 2020). Organisational public rating is determined by an organisation's ability to attract new customers and retain existing customers. Total customer satisfaction with the service provision experience affects organisation's ability to attract new customers and retain existing ones (Chen, 2017). Customer satisfaction is a key to a firm's survival in today's marketplace. It has been embraced by practitioners and academics alike as the highest goal of a company (Arichinev, et al, 2019)

For many years, Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (IBEDC) formerly known as Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) as a metamorphosis from Nigeria Electricity Power Authority (NEPA) has acquired a negative image and poor customer satisfaction for itself. Customers always complain of poor services, exaggerated electricity bills, lack of effective customer relations services, arbitrary increase in tariff rate etc. Even after NEPA, was deregulated the company did not improve much. Thus, IBEDC is still associated with all manners of negative characteristics as perceived by majority of customers, which range from corruptible tendencies and poor services rendered. In consequence, the image of the organisation has been seriously affected. Contrary to the expectations of the people, the company is at the tail end of the value chain even after the electricity value chain was unbundled, giving birth to several other companies including the Electricity Generation Company, Electricity Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN), and Electricity Distribution Company of which IBEDC is one of several other Distribution Companies (DISCO) scattered all over the country.

Quite often when the output is not enough, the customers and consumers end up not having 24hours electricity and with that customer's satisfaction has been difficult to attain by the Distribution Companies (DISCOs) Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (IBEDC) formally came into existence on 1st November 2013 as part of the unbundling of the electricity sector. The company covers the largest franchise area in Nigeria, made up of Oyo, Ogun, Osun, Kwara and parts of Niger, Ekiti and Kogi states. IBEDC has a strong technical partner Manila Electric Company (MERALCO), the largest power distribution company in the Philippines helping to ensure it meets the targeted objectives. IBEDC mission statement is distributing power, changing lives while its vision is to be the best power distribution company in Nigeria. Their corporate head office is in Ibadan, the capital of Oyo state. Public relations are a profession dedicated to the effective use of communication. Public relations strategies help professionals to plan and deliver strategic activities that work towards achieving the same goal (www.ibedc.com) retrieved 31st August 2021.

Electricity power generation has been a major challenge in Nigeria for several years. The Federal Government has made series of efforts to reorganize the power sector several times. Almost every house owner and tenants have alternate power generating sets to meet demands. In addition, both public and private corporate organisations have alternate power supply generating sets. For this reason, the power sector at the national level has a serious negative image. No wonder the power distribution companies often engage in powerful public relations campaigns to improve their image to ensure customers' satisfaction. The Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company is not left out. It is the duty of public relations to bridge the communication gaps between corporate organisations and their publics. Thus, PR plays critical roles in establishing and maintaining mutual understanding between IBEDC and its customers. By using some PR strategies to communicate its plans and programmes to its customers IBEDC seeks to earn the loyalty and understanding of the customers.

In this regard, the following PR strategies are often used by IBEDC: Radio and Television Adverts, Community engagement or Town Hall Meetings, corporate social responsibility, mass marketing, social media platforms, radio and television sponsored programmes, and calendar of engagement for weekly 250-500 customers to persuade and retain their loyalty. Despite all these efforts however, there seems not to be much confidence on the part of the customers about the positive impact of the image of the company on the consumers because

there is low customers' satisfaction among electricity consumers in Ibadan metropolis as in other parts of Oyo State. The study therefore was billed to assess the effectiveness of the IBEDC public relations strategies designed to enhance the performance of the company and to ensure customer satisfaction. The study also tried to find out the extent to which IBEDC met its set objectives. The conceptual model for this study is divided into the independent variables and the dependent variables. These variables are the key points through which the study will be guided.

The independent variable is sub divided into the public relations strategies used to satisfy IBEDC customers. The public relations strategies adopted by IBEDC are advertising, events, customer care, publicity, community engagement, corporate social responsibility, mass media, social media, direct marketing and bulk messaging group. The impact of these strategies is that it helps to influence the public opinion that has the strength to build and break a firms' customer base. Positive customer satisfaction enhances the organisations image. Organisations like IBEDC indulge in public relations activities because the way customers perceive their business is bad so they need it in order to get back their feet

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model of Public Relations on Customer Satisfaction

Source: Researchers’ Idea (2021)

Furthermore, the impact of these public relations strategies is to help IBEDC to satisfy their customers in the aspect of communicating a message in the best possible way and gain the attention of the customers. Another impact of public relations strategy on IBEDC in satisfying their customer is by creating a strong relationship with the customers in order to bring positive image of the business to the public. While trying to win the heart of the customer, it is necessary and important to communicate effectively by gaining exposure to audiences using topics of public interest and news worthy item to capture their hearts. One of the public relations strategies is corporate social responsibility; this is the major strategy that attracts customer more because it has to do with giving to the community. The people who

benefits from it are happy and they begin to sing praises of the organisation thereby giving it a good reputation and name.

For instance, IBEDC can go to any community nearby donate a new transformer or IBEDC should give discount on tariff fee for the month, all of these bring friendly rapport between the staff and the customer. Public relations strategy is way important in any organisations like IBEDC. By using these strategies, there won't be any crisis among the customers. The IBEDC staffs should be ready to listen to customer complaint and questions but without the use of these strategies, crises and quarrels among the customer will keep increasing. Therefore, it will be of good benefit if IBEDC implement the use of public relations strategies to satisfy their customers. The dependent variable is Customer satisfaction; it is centered on how the customers get satisfied by the service of IBEDC in Ibadan. The independent variables which are the public relations strategies establish the relationship with the dependent variable of the subject of the study who is the customers and consumers. The independent variables come together to give a result to the inquiry of the dependent variable which forms the basis of the research questions for the study. It is important for IBEDC to be able to meet the needs of their customers and to provide adequate solutions to any of their problems. It is very important to meet the need of customers because it always gives a good reputation and image of the company or organisation.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design and the population of the study comprises consumers of electricity from Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company in which the average population in Oyo State according to 2020 SMEDAN report was put at 7,565,108. Out of this figure, Ibadan metropolis is 3,551,961, it is assumed that all Ibadan residents are using electricity. A multistage sampling technique whereby customers of the IBEDC were ranked for the administration of questionnaire was adopted. IBEDC offices were stratified and ranked into five: (1). Capital Building Ring Road, (2). Dugbe Business hub (3) Ojo Zonal office (4) Agodi Regional Office and (5). Molete Head Office.

Furthermore, the researcher adopted the purposive sampling technique and stratification by customer population. Taro Yamane formula was adopted for the calculation of the sample

size and formula is expressed a population of 353 was finally used for distribution of questionnaire to IBEDC Consumers in Ibadan metropolis.

Results and Findings

In a bid to provide answers to the raised question on the public relations strategies used by IBEDC, (see Tablea 1 and 2) majority of the respondents with 35.4% agreed, 28.1% strongly agreed, 27.2% disagreed, while the remaining 9.4% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC staff were friendly and helpful to customers. This implies that IBEDC staff applies more of friendship and helpful PR strategies to gain customers patronage.

Also in the table, majority of the respondents with 37.4% agreed, 30.3% strongly agreed, 14.7% disagreed, while the remaining 17.6% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC staff interact with customers through the mass media. This implies that IBEDC staff also applies a system of interaction with customers through the mass media.

Table 1: Public Relations Strategies used by Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (N=353)

Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
IBEDC staff are friendly and helpful to customers	99 (28.1)	125 (35.4)	96 (27.2)	33 (9.4)
IBEDC staff interacts with customers through the mass media (Media Relations)	107 (30.3)	132(37.4)	52 (14.7)	62 (17.6)
IBEDC customer care service respond to customers questions in timely manner (Customer Relations)	98 (27.8)	104(29.5)	80(22.6)	71(20.1)
IBEDC organizes regular interactive for a with customers in Ibadan (Customer Relations)	107(30.3)			
IBEDC has a weekly sponsored television programme on BCOS, OGTV and NTA Ibadan titled “ <i>Imole de, Light</i> ” (Media Relations)	110(31.2)	151(42.8)	48(13.6)	47 (13.3)
IBEDC communicate to customers through text messages (Digital Media)	108(30.6)	141(39.9)	49(13.9)	53(15.0)
IBEDC engages in community programme and interact with members of the community regularly (Community Relations)	127(36.0)	121(34.3)	55(15.6)	69(19.5)
IBEDC advertises more on broadcast media than other mass media (Advertising)		132(37.4)	58(16.4)	36(10.2)
IBEDC creates cultural ceremonies and other events to win over the heart of their customer (Community Engagement)	120(34.0)	162(45.9)	37(10.5)	34(9.6)
Most times IBEDC run newspaper advertisement (Advertising)	19(5.5)	22(6.2)	116(32.8)	196(55.5)
IBEDC has calendar of weekly meeting with 250-500 consumers (Customer Relations)	98(27.8)	147(41.6)	47(13.3)	61(17.3)
IBEDC run online advert to pass information to the customers (Digital Media)	154(43.6)	117(33.2)	51(14.4)	31(8.8)
	155(44.2)	144(40.8)	38(10.8)	15(4.2)

Source: Field research (2021)

Key: SA= Strongly Agreed, A= Agreed, D= Disagree and SD= Strongly Disagree

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation

IBEDC Customers	N	\bar{X}	SD	T	Sig
Male	193	6.34189	53.512	4.183	.000
Female	160	4.87442	44.731	3.112	.000

Source: Field research (2021)

Data presented in Table 1 also shows that majority of the respondents with 29.5% agreed, 27.8% strongly agreed, 22.6% disagreed, while the remaining 20.1% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC customer care service responds to customer's questions in timely manner. This implies that IBEDC customer care service respond timely to customers' questions and concerns as the case may be. Also in the table, majority of the respondents with 42.8% agreed, 30.3% strongly agreed, 13.6% disagreed, while the remaining 13.3% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC organizes regular interactive forum with customers in Ibadan. This implies that IBEDC often organizes regular and interactive platform strategies with customers in Ibadan.

Also in the table, majority of the respondents with 39.9% agreed, 31.2% strongly agreed, 13.9% disagreed, while the remaining 15.0% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC has a weekly sponsored television programme on BCOS, OGTV and NTA Ibadan titled "*Imolede, Light up*". This implies that IBEDC has a weekly sponsored television programme on BCOS, OGTV and NTA Ibadan titled "*Imole de, Light up*". Also in the table, majority of the respondents with 34.3% agreed, 30.6% strongly agreed, 15.6% disagreed, while the remaining 19.5% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC communicate to customers through text messages. This implies that IBEDC from time to time communicate to customers through text messages.

Furthermore, majority of the respondents with 37.4% agreed, 36.0% strongly agreed, 16.4% disagreed, while the remaining 10.2% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC engages in community programmes and interact with members of the community regularly. This implies that IBEDC regularly engages in community programmes and interact with members of the community. Additionally, another majority of the respondents with 45.9% agreed, 34.0%

strongly agreed, 10.5% disagreed, while the remaining 9.6% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC advertises more on broadcast media than other mass media. This implies that IBEDC often advertises more on broadcast media to other mass media. In answer to another question, majority of the respondents with 55.5% strongly disagreed, 32.8% disagreed, 6.2% agreed, while the remaining 5.5% strongly agreed to the fact that IBEDC creates cultural ceremonies and other events to win over the heart of their customer.

This implies that IBEDC barely create cultural ceremonies and other events to win over the heart of their customer. Also in the table, majority of the respondents with 41.6% agreed, 27.8% strongly agreed, 13.3% disagreed, while the remaining 17.3% strongly disagreed to the fact that most times IBEDC run newspaper advertisements. This implies that most times IBEDC run newspaper advertisements when the need arises. Majority of the respondents with 33.2% agreed, 43.6% strongly agreed, 14.4% disagreed, while the remaining 8.8% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC has calendar of weekly meeting with 250-500 consumers.

This implies that IBEDC often has calendar of weekly meeting with 250-500 consumers. Lastly in the table, majority of the respondents with 44.2% strongly agreed, 40.8% agreed, 10.8% disagreed, while the remaining 4.2% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC run online advert to pass information to the customers. This implies that IBEDC often run online advert to pass information to the customers. It is evident from answers provided by the respondents that all the public relations strategies itemized in the conceptual framework are used by IBEDC.

Table 3: Level of Effectiveness of Public Relations Strategies Deployed by Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company on Customers' Satisfaction (N=353)

Effectiveness of the application of PR Strategies by IBEDC on Customers	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Customers are satisfied with the information gotten from press releases	77 (21.8)	54 (15.2)	89 (25.2)	133 (37.7)
Quality service provided by IBEDC to customer is Satisfactory	69 (19.5)	63 (17.8)	70 (19.8)	151 (42.8)
The usage of social media to communicate the activities of IBEDC is satisfactory	32(9.1)	89 (25.2)	112 (31.7)	120(34.0)
IBEDC engages in activities that ensures good relationship with its community	95 (26.9)	134 (37.9)	86 (24.4)	38 (10.8)
IBEDC engage in activities that ensures good relationship with media stations(NTA,OGTV, BCOS)	196(55.5)	96 (27.3)	39(11.0)	22 (6.2)

Source: Field Research (2021)

Key: SA= Strongly Agreed, A= Agreed, D= Disagree and SD= Strongly Disagree

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation

IBEDC Customers	N	\bar{X}	SD	T	Sig
Male	193	6.76432	54.427	7.547	.000
Female	160	4.41421	63.219	2.888	.000

Source: Field research (2021)

Table 3 provides answers to the raised questions on the effectiveness of the PR strategies of IBEDC on customer satisfaction. Majority of the respondents with 37.7% strongly disagreed, 25.2% disagreed, 21.8% agreed, while the remaining 15.2% strongly agreed to the fact that customers are satisfied with the information gotten from press releases. This implies that

IBEDC customers are not satisfied with the information gotten from press releases. Also in the table, majority of the respondents with 42.8% strongly disagreed, 19.5% disagreed, 19.8% strongly agreed, while the remaining 17.8% agreed to the fact that the quality service provided by IBEDC to customer is satisfactory. This implies that the quality service provided by IBEDC to customer is not satisfactory. Furthermore, majority of the respondents with 34.0% strongly disagreed, 31.7% disagreed, 25.2% agreed, while the remaining 9.1% strongly agreed to the fact that the usage of social media to communicate the activities of IBEDC is satisfactory. This implies that the usage of social media to communicate the activities of IBEDC is not satisfactory to customers.

Also in the table, majority of the respondents with 37.9% agreed, 26.9% strongly agreed, 24.4% disagree, while the remaining 10.8% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC engages in activities that ensure good relationship with its community. This implies that IBEDC engages in activities that ensures good relationship with its community. Lastly, majority of the respondents with 55.5% strongly agreed, 27.3% agreed, 11.0% disagree, while the remaining 6.2% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC engages in activities that ensure good relationship with media stations (NTA, OGTV, BCOS). This implies that IBEDC engages in activities that ensures good relationship with media stations. In conclusion, it is noted that majority of the respondents are not satisfied with the quality of service of IBEDC.

Table 5: Level of Customers' Satisfaction with the services of the Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (N=353)

Items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
I have electricity regularly	79(22.3)	85(24.1)	80(22.7)	109(30.9)
There is electricity when I need it	40(11.3)	60(17.0)	114(32.4)	139(39.3)
I have good relationship with IBEDC officials	79(22.3)	144(40.8)	74(21.0)	56(15.9)
The amount charged is more than electricity consumed	57(16.1)	206(58.4)	42(11.9)	48(13.6)
I am satisfied with usage of prepaid meter	54(15.3)	183(51.8)	82(23.3)	34(9.6)
I am satisfied with usage of postpaid meter IBEDC staff attends to me well	22(6.2)	40(11.3)	94(26.7)	197(55.8)

Source: Field Research (2021)

Key: SA= Strongly Agreed, A= Agreed, D= Disagree and SD= Strongly Disagree

Table 6: Mean and Standard Deviation for RQ4

IBEDC Customers	N	\bar{X}	SD	T	Sig
Male	193	7.65489	27.644	5.664	.000
Female	160	5.73632	23.939	3.453	.000

Source: Field research (2021)

Table 5 shows answers to the raised question on the methods to ascertain the level of customers' satisfaction in Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company, majority of the respondents with 30.9% strongly disagreed, 22.7% disagreed, 24.1% agree, while the remaining 22.3% strongly agreed to the fact that they have electricity regularly. This implies that customers do not have electricity regularly. Also in the table, majority of the respondents with 32.4% disagreed, 39.3% strongly disagreed, 17.0% agreed, while the remaining 11.3% strongly agreed to the fact that there is electricity when they need it. This implies that customers do not have electricity when they need it. Also in the table, majority of the respondents with 40.8% agreed, 22.3% strongly agreed, 21.0% disagree, while the remaining

15.9% strongly disagreed to the fact that they have good relationship with IBEDC officials. This implies that customers have good relationship with IBEDC officials. Furthermore in the table, majority of the respondents with 58.4% agreed, 16.1% strongly agreed, 11.9% disagreed, while the remaining 13.6% strongly disagreed to the fact that the amount charged is more than electricity consumed. This implies that the amount charged customers is more than electricity consumed. Furthermore, another majority of the respondents with 51.8% agreed, 15.3% strongly agreed, 23.3% disagreed, while the remaining 9.6% strongly disagreed that they were satisfied with usage of prepaid meter. This implies that customers are satisfied with usage of prepaid meter. Also in the table, majority of the respondents with 55.8% strongly disagreed, 26.7% disagreed, 11.3% agreed, while the remaining 6.2% strongly agreed to the fact that they were satisfied with usage of postpaid meter. This implies that customers are not satisfied with usage of postpaid meter. Lastly in the table, majority of the respondents with 30.9% agreed, 23.8% strongly agreed, 19.8% disagreed, while the remaining 25.5% strongly disagreed to the fact that IBEDC staff attends to them well. This implies that customers are well attended to by IBEDC staff. In summary, majority of the respondents confirm that they are not satisfied with the level of satisfaction given to them by Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company.

Conclusion

Empirically, findings have revealed that there exists a positive connect between the use of public relations strategies and customer's satisfaction. Since the major aim of every business is to make profit and continue to stay afloat by having its products and services patronized, consumed and appreciated by its target market (consumers), it is therefore imperative for IBEDC to device effective public relations strategies that will help communicate value to its existing and potential customers.

Thus, for the company to survive, application of effective public relations strategies is inevitable. Gone are the days when some companies thrived because customers had no choice. In this respect IBEDC must convince its customers, in order to attract their patronage. In other words, customer satisfaction has become a basis for attraction. The study therefore concludes that public relations strategies are regarded as the most significant key needed by

IBEDC towards boosting customer satisfaction which in turn will help to build a sustainable corporate image for the organisation.

Recommendation

It is hereby recommended that IBEDC should ensure that it builds a favourable image and goodwill within its locality; this would be further enhanced if efficiency in service-delivery is adequately addressed. IBEDC should establish more customer care strategies, in which existing and potential customers would be free to make suggestions and recommendations on how the firms' services could be improved.

Secondly, IBEDC should improve on its relationship with media men. A little friendly invitation to lunch or any social occasion such as cultural ceremonies and community programmes could become the albatross to good reportage and coverage of events. It is also advisable that IBEDC should increase its customer relations activities, like giving out gift items, calendars, etc., to all customers, instead of a selected few. The company should also increase its public relations activities, especially in the area of local sports sponsorship and organizing other social events to endear itself to its customers in Ibadan metropolis.

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